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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D11.3 Final business and economic assessment and exploitation plans

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/ Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission (for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates)
AIPO	Agenzia Interregionale per il Fiume Po (Italian infrastructure authority for the Po River), participant in CRISTAL
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CATI	Computer Assisted Telephone Interviews
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interview
DM	Data Management
DT	Digital Twin
ENEA	Energia Nucleare ed Energie Alternative (the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development), participant in CRISTAL
EPCIS	Electronic Product Code Information Services (a global GS1standard)
EuRIS	European River Information System
FBG	Fibre Bragg Grating
FOS	Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring
GA	Grant Agreement
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar
IoT	Internet of Things
IV	Infrastrutture Venete (an Italian infrastructure authority), participant in CRISTAL
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Waterway
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KR	Key Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L-PIT	Lukasiewicz - Poznanski Instytut Technologiczny, CRISTAL coordinator
LL	Living Lab
LSP	Logistics Service Provider
LTE	Long-Term Evolution (a standard for high-speed wireless communication)

MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (a lightweight, publish-subscribe messaging protocol)
R&I	Research and Investment
RIS	River Information Systems
SB	Smart Buoy
SCBA	Social Cost-Benefit Analysis
SCMS	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar (for IWW assets' structures)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VNF	Voies Navigables de France (the infrastructure operator for the French pilot), participant in CRISTAL
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

The CRISTAL project developed and tested within its **three pilots** a significant number of innovative solutions aimed to contribute towards increasing the performance and attractiveness of inland water transport (IWT) in Europe. These include:

- Sensor-based technologies (developed in WP2):
 - ✓ Acoustic Emission (AE) system for health monitoring of lock gates;
 - ✓ Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system for inspecting the assets' structures;
 - ✓ Intelligent Smart Buoy (SB) system for monitoring key parameters that affect the navigability;
 - ✓ Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) system for riverbed monitoring.
- Digital systems/platforms (developed in WP3 and WP5):
 - ✓ Synchro-modal Corridor Management System;
 - ✓ Digital Twin.
- Innovative Business and Governance Models (developed in WP4).

In addition to the above, pilot leaders and stakeholders involved in CRISTAL have tested a series of “own initiatives”, i.e., state-of-the-art commercially available technologies and technical solutions, to determine their feasibility for novel applications in the IWT sector.

All these innovations and new applications have been tested in three pilots deployed in three countries: Italy (WP7), France (WP8) and Poland (WP9). The pilots delivered complex sets of results comprising data collected on site, observations, different digital files, expert opinions (as responses to questionnaires and/or surveys), etc.

CRISTAL outcomes have been further analysed and evaluated for validating the innovative solutions and applications tested in the pilots within WP10.

The current report presents the final business and economic assessment carried out at the end of the project, based on previous outcomes from work packages mentioned above, as well as the final considerations regarding the exploitation of CRISTAL results, including:

- i) The exploitation and IPR strategy
- ii) Individual exploitation plans
- iii) The roadmap for exploitation of CRISTAL Project Results Beyond the Project Lifetime.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable and corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1: Alignment of D11.3 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable and task descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D11.3 Final business and economic assessment, and exploitation plans	D11.3 will identify and quantify the results generated by the consortium. It will provide an economic assessment of each of the results and provide exploitation plans with support of the Exploitation Board. The next steps with respect to Intellectual Property will be identified.	Section 2. Overview of CRISTAL Technologies and Innovative Solutions Section 4. Business Models and Economic Impacts Section 5. Exploitable Results and Exploitation Plans	Overall project results have been identified in §2 and prioritised in §5.2. Business aspects are addressed by §3 and §4.1, while a final assessment of economic impacts is presented in §4.2 and §4.3. Exploitation and IPR plans are presented in §5.
TASK			
Task 11. 2 Exploitation and Intellectual Property (IP)	The research and development activity of the project is aiming to create new knowledge and opportunities to expand market opportunities for private organisations. Best practices and recommendations To facilitate this, ALICE will perform a segmentation of stakeholders and IWT operators, infrastructure managers, suppliers and users. ALICE will also act as the liaison with other relevant projects building on their previous experience in this activity and link it to EC Strategies and with the DTLF developments.	Section 3. European Inland Waterway Transport Market Section 5. Exploitable Results and Exploitation Plans	Activities carried out by ALICE and overall market perspective is presented in §3. This is complemented by key aspects in §5, in particular the roadmap for exploitation of CRISTAL results beyond the project's lifetime.
	The objective of IP Management is to identify, qualify and protect the results generated by the consortium. The IP Manager (UNEW) will be in charge of the coordination of project IPR issues with partners . An Intellectual Property and Exploitation Board (IPEB) will be created, which includes one member of each consortium partner, to support this process. An Intellectual property log will be created and maintained	Section 5. Exploitable Results and Exploitation Plans	Activities carried out by the Intellectual Property and Exploitation Board (IPEB) coordinated by UNEW, and content of IPEB log are presented in §5 and Annex. Detailed exploitation plans (per each partner), as well as a general roadmap for the project as a whole have been defined with respect to project outcomes, primarily the KERs.

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Deliverable D11.3 is divided in six main sections, with additional supporting information included in the annex.

Section 1 Executive Summary, i.e., the current one, introduces first (§1.1) the deliverable in the context of the CRISTAL project, in general, and of work package (*WP11 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation*), in particular. The objective of the work reported in the deliverable is clearly defined, along with the specific activities carried out to reach the objective.

Then, the content of the report is mapped against the description of the relevant task in the CRISTAL project, and of deliverable reporting the outcomes of this specific task (§1.2).

The current subsection (§1.3) provides more details about the structure and the content of this deliverable report.

Section 2 overviews the CRISTAL project's innovative results, including:

- Technologies developed and tested within the project (sensor-based technologies and digital systems);
- Pilots' "own initiatives";
- Roadmaps and governance models.

Section 3 presents an analysis of the current state of the European Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) market, its structural challenges, and future opportunities, with particular emphasis on policy, governance, and innovation needs. It establishes the strategic context for the CRISTAL project results (as summarised in Section 2) and positions them within ongoing European transport, logistics, and climate policy discussions, including recommendations promoted by ALICE (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration).

Section 4 is dedicated to a final assessment of business models and economic impacts. Sub-section 4.1 presents a summary of development and refinement of CRISTAL business models (BMs), including their final refined version, along with specific conclusions and recommendation. Sub-section 4.2 presents the update of cost-benefit analysis (using the tool developed in WP4) based on final inputs from Living labs (LLs) and pilots. In addition, sub-section 4.3 presents a case study focused on potential economic impacts on the Polish market.

Section 5 is based on activities carried out by the project's IPEB, and comprises the exploitation and IPR strategy (§5.1), the final prioritised key exploitable results (KERs) and their links to initially foreseen key results (KRs) in §5.2, the project partners' individual exploitation plans (§5.3) and the CRISTAL roadmap for exploitation beyond the project's lifetime (§5.4).

Conclusions regarding all connected issues presented throughout §2 to §5 are summarised in **Section 6**.

The **Annex** includes the detailed spreadsheet, which was part of the IPEB log, along with the specific notes associated to each IPEB meeting. The spreadsheet summarises key aspects such as background, foreground (protectable and non-protectable), exploitation activities to be pursued after the project end, dissemination, etc., for each CRISTAL partner.

2. Overview of CRISTAL Technologies and Innovative Solutions

2.1. Context

Work carried out in previous work packages of the CRISTAL project (WP2, WP3 and WP5) focused on developing sensor-based technologies and digital solutions for different applications in IWW environment, which would contribute towards achieving the high-level objectives of the project and the associated KPIs. These technologies have been further deployed and tested in the project River Pilots (WP7, WP8 and WP9).

In addition to the technologies developed within the project, pilot leaders and stakeholders involved in CRISTAL also considered, tested and assessed a series of state-of-the-art commercially available technologies and technical solutions to determine their feasibility for novel applications in the Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) sector.

2.2. CRISTAL Technologies

2.2.1. Sensor-based technologies

Four sensor-based technologies have been developed, tested and evaluated in the CRISTAL project. The development of these technologies has been reported in detail in deliverable reports D2.1 (CRISTAL, 2022), D2.2 (CRISTAL, 2024a) and D2.3 (CRISTAL, 2025a) of the CRISTAL project.

Two of these technologies (Acoustic Emission, AE, and Subsurface Inspection Radar, SIR) have been designed to support infrastructure operators in assessing the structural health of critical elements of infrastructure assets (lock gates, in the case of AE, and engineered structures such as lock walls, groundworks, dams, etc., in the case of SIR). Monitoring and/or inspecting the infrastructure condition with such modern techniques conditions is a prerequisite for improving maintenance planning and implement preventive and predictive maintenance processes. The other two (Fibre Optic Sensors, FOS, and Smart Buoys, SB) have been designed to acquire and communicate key data in IWT environment (i.e., water depth, bridge gauges, level of sediment on riverbed, operating vessels, etc.) and provide such enhanced information to stakeholders including infrastructure managers, operators and other end users.

Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)

Developed by CERTH, this system used piezoelectric sensors to detect high-frequency stress waves generated by material deformation or microcracks in metallic structures, such as lock gates. The technology aimed to provide early warnings of potential failures, enabling predictive maintenance and reducing unexpected downtime.

The AE system is able to provide early-warning indicators and localise the active damage sources, enabling condition-based maintenance and reduction of unplanned outages. The system consists of wideband piezoelectric AE sensors, low-noise preamplifiers, a multi-channel acquisition unit with precise time synchronisation, and a signal-processing pipeline for hit detection, feature extraction (e.g., amplitude, energy, RA value, average frequency), event clustering/localisation, and severity classification. Thereby, the output data usable by CRISTAL's Data Management (DM) and Digital Twin (DT) include event counts and rates, energy and frequency-based descriptors, source location estimates, and health indicators that can be supplied to and consumed by the DT/SCMS, or potentially links to other external interested stakeholder. The system uses developed proprietary libraries, which enable to detect the build-up of gate's microcracks in the vicinity of the sensors coming from possible metallic plastic deformations and,

thereby, to provide an early warning of large failures caused by this buildup, and general out of the normal events like gate's pistons' failure, objects bouncing against the gates, precipitations at the bottom of the water lock trench obscuring the normal gate operation etc. The deviation from a normal operating space is an indication/prediction of upcoming gate failures. AE sensors are mounted on the gate and near the parts of the gate that are of interest to inspect, as shown in Figure 1. The AE sensors can be observed on the top of the gate, below the red magnetic holders.

Figure 1: AE sensors mounted on a lock gate

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

This technology, developed by UNEW and EUMO, uses Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) equipment for non-invasive inspection of infrastructure assets like lock walls, groundworks and dams. The primary goal was to detect subsurface anomalies such as cracks, voids, or material deterioration, thereby enabling a shift from corrective to preventive and predictive maintenance. The system was designed to be modular and semi-automated, capable of generating 3D subsurface imagery.

Currently, visual inspections of lock chambers are carried out within scheduled maintenance activities, which can detect just a limited number of potential issues, and mostly surface ones. The SIR system uses state-of-the-art radar techniques designed for in-depth scanning (GPR), which is typically used for earthworks, masonry and concrete structure inspection, to detect, localise and profile features (i.e., structural anomalies) concealed within such subsurface media. Returned data can be analysed to determine both quantitative (e.g., depth, footprint, etc.) and qualitative (e.g., shape, complexity, composition, etc.) feature properties.

The developed SIR system combines a bespoke physical hardware platform, comprising state-of-the-art radar technology integrated with a dedicated motorised positioning frame, and a software-driven data analytics workflow, responsible for converting raw radar measurement data into more intuitive 3D spatial profiles of subsurface Features of Interest (Fols), with a primary focus on the detection and characterisation of voids. The platform is operated by a crane and positioned over the lock wall (Figure

2a). A quadrant volume scanning begins with the radar antenna positioned at a reference corner of the frame, marked by the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) antenna (Figure 2b, yellow arrows showing the scanning sequences). Data collection is semi-automated, as the operator has to initiate the scan by manually triggering the GPR software, which starts data recording. After completing the quadrant scanning, the rig is re-positioned by the crane to another quadrant on the wall (Figure 2c).

Figure 2: Data collection with SIR technology - procedure for lock walls

The bespoke SIR system frame was designed to allow semi-automated subsurface inspection of vertical and sloping walls or structures (such as lock walls and dams), as opposed to conventional GPR, which is manually operated and most frequently applied to horizontal surfaces (i.e., the ground).

Smart Buoys (SB)

The Smart Buoy (SB) system was developed Ł-PIT for the Polish pilot, these buoys were equipped with sensors to measure parameters like water level, current speed, temperature, and bridge clearance. They were designed to provide real-time environmental data to improve navigational safety and efficiency on free-flowing rivers like the Vistula.

The SB system is an integrated environmental monitoring and navigation support platform designed for inland waterways, which combines floating sensor nodes, bridge-mounted devices, vessel transponders, and a central server application into a unified architecture for real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis.

The SB system (Figure 3) consists of two functional sub-systems:

- Buoy-based sensing and communication – Each buoy is equipped with sensors that measure water depth, current velocity, temperature, tilt, and atmospheric conditions. It also receives data on bridge clearance via wireless links and detects vessel traffic through an Automatic Identification System (AIS) receiver. A sealed electronics insert houses the power supply, processing unit, and communication modules, ensuring durability in harsh river environments. Data is logged locally and transmitted in real time via Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM)/ LTE (Long-Term Evolution standard for high-speed wireless communication networks).

- Backend infrastructure – A central server application ingests buoy data over the MQTT protocol (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport lightweight messaging protocol), processes it, and distributes it to external applications such as digital twin and smart canal management systems.

Figure 3: SB System structure and data flow

The SB prototype adapts standard 700 mm navigation buoys with modular electronics, including an STM32-based carrier board, Controller Area Network (CAN) interfaces, GNSS, and an LTE IoT module for remote data transmission.

Bridge-mounted devices use radar sensors to measure vertical clearance and broadcast it via AIS AtoN, while vessel transponders (e.g., NOMAD2 Class B) supply identity and position data to nearby buoys. Additional deck buoys support AIS testing.

All buoy data is sent over MQTT, with configuration files defining measurement cycles and communication parameters. Server-side software parses telemetry and events, distributing them to navigation authorities, research systems, and Electronic Product Code Information Services (EPCIS)-compliant long-term data platforms.

The SB system enhances safety and situational awareness in waterways by:

- Providing real-time hydrological and environmental data.
- Broadcasting bridge clearance information for vessel passage safety.
- Detecting and tracking vessel traffic.
- Supporting integration with external systems for predictive analysis, fleet management, and environmental monitoring.

Through modular design, robust communication, and energy-optimised operation, the SB system demonstrates a scalable and cost-effective approach to modernising the monitoring of inland waterway infrastructure.

Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)

Developed by ENEA, this technology uses Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors to monitor sediment buildup in critical sections of free-flowing waterways like the Po River. Unlike traditional daily bathymetric surveys, FOS may offer continuous, real-time monitoring with low environmental impact. The technology, at TRL 4, aimed to provide Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on navigability directly to infrastructure managers

via smart dashboards. The technical setup involved chaining together weighing pads housing the fibre optics, made from durable materials for submarine applications. However, a significant bottleneck identified was the high installation cost, estimated at €250,000 for a prototype, which was not affordable within the project budget and therefore limited testing to the laboratory.

FBG technology is highly mature and widely employed across diverse industrial sectors for critical applications. In the CRISTAL project, FBG technology was used to develop a submerged weighing platform. The advantage is that it uses a completely passive optical operating principle, eliminating the need for electrical power at the measurement point. The weighing platform features a straightforward mechanical design based on the bending plate principle, which reduces maintenance requirements. The weighing platform is intended to indirectly estimate the height of the sediments heap through the direct measurement of its weight.

Figure 4 illustrates the operating principle of the FOS. The top drawing shows a cross-section of the river and its riverbed, with an array of weighing pads (the red segments) installed slightly beneath the surface. These pads are connected in series by a fibre optic cable (dark-green line), which transmits signals from the FBG sensors embedded in the pads. The enlarged inset schematically depicts the force (weight) exerted by the sediments heap on a pad. The middle drawing represents the pad in its 'reference condition', i.e., with no load applied. For clarity, the plate is shown unburied, with its upper surface aligned with the riverbed; however, any load present in the installation setup can still be considered part of the reference condition. The bottom drawing illustrates the loaded condition, where the plate is activated (bent) under the weight of deposited sediments. The force acting on the pad is generated by the sediments' weight resting directly on the plate (with negligible non-vertical forces due to the muddy nature of the heap), thereby enabling the indirect estimation of the sediments heap height through the direct measurement of its weight.

Figure 4: Operating principle of FOS

2.2.2. Digital Systems

Digital Twins (DTs)

Developed by Fraunhofer within WP5, the DTs are virtual representations of physical assets (like locks or river segments) that aggregated data from various sensors (FOS, AE, SIR, SB).

The functionality of the Smart Inland Waterway Monitor was covered by three Digital Twins: DT Lock, DT Buoy, and DT Water Level. Each Digital Twin addresses specific aspects of inland navigation:

- **DT Lock:** Monitors the condition of lock gates and walls, providing alerts about maintenance needs and potential failures. This allows for predictive maintenance and enhances the safety and efficiency of lock operations.
- **DT Buoy:** Visualises various measured data related to buoys, such as water depth, flow speed, and environmental conditions. This information is crucial for assessing navigability and planning safe routes for vessels.
- **DT Water Level:** Forecasts water levels using historical and real-time data, enabling reliable predictions of navigability conditions. This is essential for proactive planning and risk mitigation in critical situations.

By implementing these Digital Twins, the Smart Inland Waterway Monitor enhances safety on inland waterways, improves the efficiency of shipping traffic, and reduces response times in critical situations.

The DTs use historical and real-time data to provide forecasts, alerts, and visualisations to support decision-making for both transport operators and infrastructure managers. For example, the DT-Water Level uses historical data and machine learning to forecast navigability, while the DT-Locks analyses AE and SIR data to provide maintenance recommendations. The use cases were tested across all three pilots. The technical architecture was designed to be modular and scalable, using open-source components and state-of-the-art technologies (Java, Python, Angular, Docker) to ensure maintainability and future expansion.

Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS)

The Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is a platform that aims to enhance the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of inland waterway transport in EU. The SCMS, developed by CERTH within WP3, is an online platform designed to function as a single point of information for all stakeholders. It consolidated data from the DTs and external sources (like EuRIS) to provide early warnings, identify the impact of disruptions, and suggest Synchro-modal re-routing options involving road and rail.

The SCMS is designed to support various stakeholders involved in inland waterway transport, such as shippers, carriers, terminal operators, authorities, policy makers, and researchers. By using the platform, users can benefit from improved decision making, increased reliability and resilience, reduced costs and emissions, and enhanced competitiveness and innovation.

SCMS Features are:

- **Alerting system** - It notifies users of any real-time or forecasted disruptions on the waterways, such as accidents, congestion, weather conditions, water levels, etc.
- **Data collecting** - Data extraction from sensors placed throughout the rivers that collect and transmit information on various parameters, such as traffic flows, vessel positions, emissions, fuel consumption, etc.
- **Personalisation** - Personalised preferences section that allows users to customise their settings and preferences according to their needs and interests, such as preferred routes, modes of transport, cargo types, etc.

- **Route Planning** - Route planning assessment that helps users to plan their trips on the waterways and optimise their costs, time and environmental impact. The platform also offers multimodal rerouting capabilities in case of unexpected events or changes in the conditions.
- **Corridor metrics** - Corridor observatory that includes corridor-specific key performance indicators (KPIs) as well as operational metrics that measure and monitor the performance of the waterway transport system and its impact on the economy, society, and environment.

2.3. Pilots' "own initiatives"

The pilots' "own initiatives" include out-of-the-shelf technologies and/or innovative solutions that were of interest to stakeholders involved in the pilots due to their potential for new applications in the IWT sector. A summary of the pilots' "own initiatives" is presented further.

An initiative implemented as part of the Polish pilot was the organization of cargo voyages on the Vistula River. Although this initiative involved a large number of entities and was of interest to many external stakeholders, it did not involve the implementation of a specific technology (except for the smart buoys described above) and is therefore not described in this chapter.

2.3.1. Italian Pilot (WP7)

The Navigability Conditions Prediction Model and Smart Bulletin (AIPo, ENEA) combines a statistical probability model with a machine-learning model to produce daily and ten-day navigability forecasts, section by section, for different vessel drafts. The Smart Bulletin aggregates this into color-coded outputs and feeds data into the SCMS. This represents a significant step forward from the current Notice to Skippers system, which only provides measured depths without forecasts.

Cold Ironing, also known as shore power or shore-to-ship power, consists of connecting a docked ship to the port's electrical grid to power its onboard systems (lights, refrigeration, HVAC) instead of running its own noisy, polluting diesel generators. This technical solution was investigated as a feasibility study by Infrastrutture Venete (IV), which explored the system-wide deployment of shore-power infrastructure along the Po-Brondolo and Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterways. While no field test has yet been conducted, detailed engineering designs were completed for multiple landing points, defining phased implementation scenarios. Expected impacts include significant reductions in NO_x, PM, and CO₂ emissions during mooring operations and improved readiness for hybrid-electric vessels. The study highlights the environmental and strategic value of shore power, although implementation requires further investment.

2.3.2. French Pilot (WP8)

CEDRE is a technology developed by VNF, which links the transport management systems of freight operators directly to the VNF system so that freight declarations enter the Electronic Reporting International Notification Message (ERINOT) format automatically. ERINOT is used for the reporting of voyage-related information for both dangerous and non-dangerous goods carried on-board by vessels sailing on inland waterways (European Union, 2010). The first transporter has already connected successfully, and a second one is onboarding. Solutions for the costs are under investigation to improve the attractiveness to other stakeholders. The data generated by CEDRE are aimed to reduce administrative efforts and encourage a modal shift toward inland waterways while providing more reliable information for route optimisation, fee calculation and infrastructure planning.

Fluv'IOTe is another technology developed by VNF, which applies cameras and artificial-intelligence analysis to geolocate barges that are not equipped with AIS transponders and indicate mooring occupancy. Initial tracker trials preceded CRISTAL. In 2023 camera-based tests began, and during 2024 image outputs were cross-checked with AIS data. Additional machine-learning work is still required, and

quay-occupancy results are not yet disseminated to users, but the tool already raises safety and reliability by detecting vessels that are out of place.

Smart Buoys (different to the SBs developed in CRISTAL) equipped with GPS were installed on the Moselle River to support flood management. The first field tests revealed excessive movement alerts, and the chosen mitigation reduced battery life which caused the buoys to switch off. Because the devices do not yet satisfy VNF technical criteria, further research and development is needed, and no operational impact has been achieved so far.

2.4. Roadmaps and Governance Models

The CRISTAL project has demonstrated that the successful modernisation of inland waterway transport depends on the combined evolution of **technology, governance, and implementation roadmaps**. Across three contrasting pilot contexts – in France, Italy, and Poland - the project validated a **generic Living Lab-based governance framework** capable of structuring stakeholder engagement, aligning institutional responsibilities, and guiding the deployment of digital and monitoring technologies. Rather than producing a single prescriptive roadmap, CRISTAL delivered a **flexible governance-driven pathway**, showing how implementation trajectories must be adapted to local maturity levels, data availability, and institutional structures. This approach ensures that innovation is embedded within real operational and policy environments, rather than remaining isolated at pilot level.

A core outcome of CRISTAL is the definition of **practical roadmaps for technology and governance co-deployment**. The pilots converged on a shared sequence of actions: strengthening data foundations, deploying technologies incrementally at asset level, integrating new tools with existing systems, and anchoring responsibilities within stable institutions. France illustrated a roadmap centred on system integration and data harmonization within a mature governance structure; Italy demonstrated how governance renewal and stakeholder alignment are prerequisites for technological uptake; and Poland highlighted a roadmap focused on foundational investments in infrastructure, hydrological monitoring, and national coordination. Together, these experiences confirm that roadmaps must be **phased, evidence-based, and governance-led**, with clear roles, ownership, and long-term investment logic.

From a governance perspective, CRISTAL's main contribution lies in proving that **technology adoption is inseparable from institutional capacity and leadership**. The Living Lab model functioned as a governance accelerator, enabling co-creation, trust-building, and shared prioritisation among public authorities, infrastructure managers, operators, and users. Strong leadership and clear mandates emerged as decisive factors in translating pilot results into future action, while fragmented responsibilities and weak coordination slowed progress regardless of technological readiness. Overall, CRISTAL delivers a transferable governance and implementation blueprint: digital innovation can enhance resilience, reliability, and sustainability of inland waterways only when embedded in coherent governance models and supported by realistic, staged roadmaps. This integrated approach provides a solid foundation for scaling CRISTAL outcomes across European inland waterway corridors and supporting long-term climate-resilient transport strategies.

3. European Inland Waterway Transport Market

This section presents an analysis of the current state of the European Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) market, its structural challenges, and future opportunities, with particular emphasis on policy, governance, and innovation needs. It establishes the strategic context for the CRISTAL project results (as summarised in Section 2) and positions them within ongoing European transport, logistics, and climate policy discussions, including recommendations promoted by ALICE (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration), which is a pre-requisite for designing the CRISTAL exploitation plan (including individual plans per partners, and the overall roadmap for exploitation beyond the project's lifetime).

3.1. Overview of European IWT Market

3.1.1. Macro-ECONOMICS Overview

Europe experienced modest economic recovery in 2024, with EU GDP growing +1.0%, driven mainly by private consumption as inflation eased. Global GDP grew +3.3%, but geopolitical tensions, the Red Sea crisis, and anticipated US tariffs caused uncertainty in trade and investment.

- Inflation fell to 2.6% in 2024 and is projected to decline further.
- Trade growth was subdued (+3.3% globally), with fragmentation and “friendshoring” reshaping supply chains.
- Commodity markets stabilised, with falling oil prices offering relief to transport operators, although gas and agricultural markets remained volatile.

3.1.2. Problem Definition

The European Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) sector represents a strategically important but structurally underexploited component of the EU transport system. Despite a network of more than 37,000 km of navigable waterways connecting 13 Member States, IWT currently accounts for only around 5% of the EU freight modal split, a share that has slightly declined over the last decade. This contrasts sharply with the growing policy ambition to shift freight away from road transport in support of climate, congestion, and energy objectives.

IWT in Europe is still struggling to compete with rail and remains the last mode to be used by logistics stakeholders

“Over the last decade, modal split shares have overall decreased slightly for IWT and rail at the level of the EU-27, while those of road transport have slightly increased. IWT lost 2.4 percentage points in the last 10 years, reaching 5.0% in 2023, its lowest level since 2005. It is well behind road transport (78.1% in 2023, +4.2 percentage points in the last 10 years) and rail transport (16.9%, -1.8 percentage points in the last 10 years). As many EU countries do not have inland waterways, the overall modal split of IWT at the EU level should not be used as a performance indicator for the success of inland waterway transport in the EU.”¹

Several structural barriers explain this situation. From a market perspective, IWT is often perceived by shippers and logistics service providers as a secondary or “last-choice” mode, primarily suitable for bulk and low-value cargo. This perception is reinforced by concerns over reliability, limited visibility of operational conditions, fragmented governance, and insufficient integration with multimodal logistics

¹ Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine (CCNR) - 2025 Annual Market Observation report. Available at: https://inland-navigation-market.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/CCNR_annual_report_EN_2025_WEB.pdf

chains. As a result, even in regions where waterways are physically available, IWT is frequently excluded at an early stage of logistics planning.

Figure 5: IWT market share (source: CCNR 2025 annual report)

* The values for Italy (2024), Finland (2017, 2018), the United Kingdom (2024) and Serbia (2017) are not available

At the same time, external pressures are intensifying. Climate change is increasing the frequency and severity of extreme hydrological events, directly affecting navigability and infrastructure availability. Aging infrastructure assets, particularly locks and fairways, require smarter maintenance strategies but face long investment cycles and constrained public budgets. These trends underline that the competitiveness challenge of IWT is no longer only a cost issue, but increasingly one of reliability, resilience, and system transparency.

CRISTAL directly addresses the defined problem by targeting the structural causes of underperformance, rather than focusing solely on incremental efficiency gains. Indeed, CRISTAL develops innovative solutions to unlock IWT potential in underused rivers and canals. CRISTAL approach embraces existing challenges through its innovations and governance models to increase the Inland Waterways Transportation use and awareness as highlighted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The CRISTAL project approach – problem and solution mapping (presented at the UNECE in Geneva – September 2024)

In conclusion, the European IWT sector faces a structural paradox: while it offers strong intrinsic advantages in terms of energy efficiency, emissions performance, and capacity, it remains marginal in logistics decision-making due to persistent shortcomings in reliability, resilience, transparency, and integration with modern supply chains. These challenges are amplified by climate change, aging infrastructure, and fragmented governance frameworks, which together undermine confidence among market actors and limit investment appetite. Addressing this situation requires a shift from viewing inland waterways as static infrastructure assets towards managing them as dynamic, data-driven transport systems. This is precisely the gap that CRISTAL addresses by targeting the systemic causes of underperformance and by demonstrating how digitalisation, predictive capabilities, and coordinated governance can restore IWT's role as a credible, competitive, and resilient component of the European multimodal transport system.

3.2. Segmentation of target market

From a business and exploitation perspective, the CRISTAL project results address a multi-layered market, comprising distinct but interdependent stakeholder groups. This segmentation was developed as part of the Task 11.2 "Exploitation and Intellectual property", in which ALICE had to perform this assessment. 172 stakeholders were identified, according to data provided by pilots based on the baseline summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: IWT stakeholders' segmentation

GEOGRAPHICAL AREA	PILOT	SOLUTIONS	CATEGORY	KEY STAKEHOLDER
MOSELLE	FRENCH	SCMS	IWT industry and business	Good owners
SEINE	ITALIAN	All	IWT policy and government	LSPs, 3PL, 4PL, 5PL
ALL FRENCH RIVERS	POLISH		Others	Barge operators
				Freight forwarders
VISTULA				Road operators
ODRA				Terminal operators (handling operation)
ALL POLISH RIVERS				Infrastructure managers
PO				Rail operators
ALL ITALIAN RIVERS				IT providers
OTHER				Regulation public local body
				Inland ports
				EU
				Governmental bodies
				Others

A definition was provided for each stakeholder category, to facilitate the understanding and the classification. In close collaboration with University of Antwerp and aligned with the outcomes from deliverable D4.1 "Detailed requirements for the assessment method" (CRISTAL, 2023a), the key stakeholders have been defined in Table 3.

Table 3: Key stakeholders' definition

KEY STAKEHOLDERS	DEFINITION
Good owners	the company who owns good such as shipper
LSPs, 3PL, 4PL, 5PL	partial or full logistics service & transportation management
Barge operators	the company who is responsible for the operation, management and transportation services related to barges
Freight forwarders	origin to a destination on behalf of shippers/good owners (often utilizing multiple carriers and modes of transport)
Road operators	Ensure the transportation of goods on the road
Terminal operators (handling operation)	Manage and operate logistics terminals (responsible of various activities)
Infrastructure managers	Manage logistics/terminals infrastructures
Rail operators	Manage and operate rail
IT providers	Provide IT services and solution
Regulation public local body	Regional body who takes the decision and regulates activities
Inland ports	Ports in the hinterland
EU	European Union Commission
Governmental bodies	State
Others	If a stakeholder is missing

The stakeholder segmentation presented in Table 2 and Table 3 reflects the inherently multi-actor nature of the inland waterway transport (IWT) ecosystem and underlines why isolated technological solutions have historically failed to achieve market uptake. The 172 stakeholders identified across the three CRISTAL pilots confirm that value creation in IWT depends on coordinated action among infrastructure managers, transport operators, logistics actors, technology providers, and public authorities.

Infrastructure managers and waterway authorities

Infrastructure managers and waterway authorities represent a core primary market segment for CRISTAL solutions. They are responsible for the availability, safety, and resilience of waterways and assets such as locks, bridges, and fairways. As shown in the tables, this group has a strong operational mandate but is often constrained by limited budgets, aging infrastructure, and reactive maintenance practices.

CRISTAL directly addresses the needs of this segment through sensor-based monitoring, Digital Twins, and predictive maintenance tools. The value proposition for this group is primarily risk reduction, improved asset lifetime management, and more efficient allocation of maintenance resources, rather than short-term cost savings. From a business perspective, this segment represents a stable demand base, often acting as a public or semi-public buyer, and is critical for enabling downstream market adoption.

Transport operators and vessel owners

Transport operators and vessel owners form a second key segment, but with different incentives. Their primary concerns relate to reliability, predictability, and operational continuity, especially under variable hydrological conditions. The tables show that this group is fragmented, often composed of small and medium-sized enterprises, which increases sensitivity to disruptions and limits investment capacity.

For this segment, CRISTAL's Digital Twin and SCMS solutions deliver value mainly through improved situational awareness, reduced uncertainty, and better planning and re-routing options. Importantly, the benefits are indirect: operators do not necessarily seek new digital tools per se, but rather more dependable services and reduced exposure to unexpected delays and costs. This explains why adoption depends on system-wide deployment rather than individual uptake.

Logistics service providers and shippers

Logistics service providers and shippers constitute a strategically important but traditionally under-engaged segment within IWT. As reflected in the stakeholder tables, these actors typically operate across multiple modes and select transport options based on reliability, visibility, and integration into end-to-end supply chains.

For this segment, CRISTAL does not primarily offer new hardware or standalone applications, but rather a framework that makes IWT a viable and trustworthy option within multimodal logistics planning.

Ports, terminals, and intermodal nodes

Ports and terminals act as interface actors between infrastructure, transport operators, and logistics chains. The segmentation tables highlight their dual role as operational service providers and data generators. Inefficiencies or lack of coordination at this level often negate upstream or downstream gains.

CRISTAL solutions support this segment by enabling better coordination, reduced waiting times, and improved data exchange with both infrastructure managers and logistics operators. From an exploitation perspective, ports and terminals can act as early adopters and aggregators, facilitating corridor-level deployment of CRISTAL solutions.

Technology providers, system integrators, and research actors

Technology providers and system integrators represent an enabling segment rather than a final market. Their inclusion in the segmentation reflects CRISTAL's emphasis on interoperability, modularity, and openness, which are prerequisites for scalability beyond pilot sites.

This segment is essential for exploitation pathways, as it allows CRISTAL results to be embedded into commercial products, services, and public procurement frameworks

Public authorities and policy makers

Finally, public authorities and policy makers form a transversal segment influencing all others. As indicated in the tables, their role extends beyond regulation to include funding, planning, and coordination across regions and borders.

3.3. Market size & trends

3.3.1. Why Inland Waterway Freight Transport Matters?

The inland waterway freight transport market comprises economic actors, including companies, sole owners, and partnerships, providing cargo transport services on rivers, canals, lakes, and intracoastal waterways. The market scope is limited to transport services and related activities that involve commercial exchanges between parties or delivery to final customers.

In the European context, inland waterways play a strategically important role in freight transport and hold significant untapped potential to increase their modal share. Inland waterway transport is characterised by high energy efficiency, operational reliability, and substantial carrying capacity, particularly when compared with road transport, which increasingly suffers from congestion, capacity constraints, and environmental pressures.

As an alternative to road and rail, inland waterway transport offers a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable solution. It consumes less energy per tonne-kilometre than road and rail transport, while also generating lower noise emissions. In addition, inland waterways provide a high level of safety, especially for the transport of hazardous goods, and contribute to relieving traffic congestion in densely populated areas by shifting freight flows away from overloaded road networks².

3.3.2. Market Trends and Projection

The European inland water freight transport market is experiencing steady growth driven by structural shifts in freight demand, regulatory priorities, and evolving logistics strategies. According to industry analysts and based on the report by Mordor Intelligence³, the market is projected to expand from an estimated USD 44.1 billion in 2025 to USD 53 billion by 2030, at a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of approximately 3.7–3.8 % over the forecast period.

Sustainability and Policy-Driven Modal Shift

A significant trend shaping the market is the growing demand for low-carbon, cost-efficient freight corridors. Shippers and logistics planners are increasingly prioritising transport modes that align with the European Green Deal's emissions reduction targets, especially as regulatory frameworks such as carbon pricing and stricter emission standards take firmer hold. This policy environment supports a gradual modal shift from road toward inland waterways, where energy and emissions performance per tonne-kilometre is favourable.

² Mordor Intelligence (2023). Europe Inland Water Freight Transport Market- Growth, Trends, Covid-19 Impact, and Forecasts (2023-2028). Available at: <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/report/europe-inland-water-cargo-transportation-market>

³ Mordor Intelligence (2025). Europe Inland Water Freight Transport Market Size & Share Analysis - Growth Trends and Forecast (2025 - 2030). Available at: <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-inland-water-freight-transport-market>

Moreover, environmental and sustainability considerations may favour increased use of IWT over road freight: inland waterways are more energy-efficient and have lower greenhouse gas emissions per ton-km compared to road transport; this could become more relevant under EU decarbonisation policies⁴.

Fleet Modernisation and Digital Integration

Responding to both regulatory pressures and competitive dynamics, operators are upgrading traditional barge fleets and deploying digital systems that enhance supply-chain visibility and operational efficiency. Investments in modern propulsion technologies, retrofitting of existing vessels to meet tighter emission requirements, and adoption of digital traffic and cargo management tools are increasingly observed across Western and Central European waterways.

Digitalisation trends include wider use of River Information Services and other data-driven decision support platforms, which contribute to improved planning, reduced administrative delays, and stronger integration with intermodal hubs such as rail and deep-sea ports (Mordor Intelligence, 2025).

Emerging Challenges and Resilience Trends

Despite this positive outlook, recent operational experiences underline that environmental variability remains a key trend affecting market performance. Prolonged droughts and heatwaves in 2025 have led to unprecedented low water levels on major arteries such as the Rhine, Danube or Vistula, reducing vessel payloads, increasing freight costs, and highlighting the vulnerability of inland freight corridors to climate change⁵.

These conditions emphasise the growing importance of risk mitigation strategies, adaptive planning tools, and digital forecasting systems, all areas where CRISTAL's monitoring and predictive solutions provide direct value.

3.4. Challenges and opportunities

However, long-term growth depends on overcoming structural constraints (e.g. modernising infrastructure (locks, fairways) as experienced within CRISTAL, improving intermodal linkages (ports, rail/road connections), and regulatory support. Several industry stakeholders argue for more balanced transport policies that better reflect IWT's environmental benefits.

3.4.1. IWT Challenges

Lack of integration of IWT in the supply chain

Although inland waterway transport (IWT) in Europe offers significant advantages notably lower energy consumption, environmental benefits, and large carrying capacity compared to road transport, it remains insufficiently integrated into supply-chain and logistics systems. One of the main obstacles is the fragmented and often inadequate infrastructure: many inland ports and terminals lack the capacity or equipment for modern, efficient transshipment and intermodal operations, which harms the ability to link waterways with rail or road legs.

Moreover, there is a lack of coordinated physical and digital connectivity: for IWT to function smoothly in multimodal logistics, inland waterways must be connected with other transport modes, and digital

⁴ Niu, T, Shao, Z, Zhu, G (2024). Toward greener freight: Overview of inland waterway transport for freight in the European Union. International Council on Clean Transportation. Available at: https://theicct.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/ID-152-%E2%80%93Inland-waterway_final.pdf

⁵The Guardian (2025). Low water levels push up shipping costs on Europe's rivers amid heatwave. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2025/jul/07/low-water-levels-shipping-europe-rivers-heatwave-rhine>

systems need to allow visibility of terminals, real-time capacity, and efficient cargo tracking, but such integration remains limited.

In 2025, ALICE organised two workshops, one online and one on site.

The first workshop held in April was in collaboration with the MultiRELOAD project which developed digital solutions for water monitoring.⁶

Figure 7: Poster and Screenshot for workshop organised by ALICE on 10th April 2025

Online attendees answered a set of questions through SLIDO which enabled getting practical insight such as the workshop hosted by ALICE at the Transport Logistics Munich 2025⁷.

Both workshops confirmed the previous statement: Around 70% of participants identified the lack of digital infrastructure and data sharing as the biggest barrier to adopting advanced tools such as Digital Twins. Without reliable and shared information, inland waterways remain difficult to plan and manage within modern logistics operations.

Operational reliability is also a significant issue. Waterway transport is vulnerable to hydrological variability as faced by the Polish pilot on the Vistula (e.g., low-water periods), aging infrastructure, and maintenance back-logs, all of which undermine consistency and predictability in supply-chain planning.

Finally, the organisational structure of the inland waterway sector, often composed of many small operators and the absence of regular, standardised freight services or scheduled lines make it harder for shippers and forwarders to rely on IWT in the same way they do on road or rail.

Because of these constraints, infrastructure deficiencies, poor intermodal connectivity, lack of digital/organisational integration, and reliability issues, inland waterways often remain marginal to supply-chain networks, used mainly for certain bulk or heavy cargo, but seldom as a backbone of a seamless multimodal logistics chain.

Reliability, Climate Vulnerability and Aging Infrastructures

Reliability is one of the main concerns affecting IWT competitiveness. Climate-related events such as low water levels, floods, and droughts are becoming more frequent and directly impact navigability, cargo

⁶ ALICE (2025). [WORKSHOP] Advancing Inland Waterways with Digital Twins – Exploring CRISTAL project innovations and MultiRELOAD project demonstrator. Available at: <https://www.etp-logistics.eu/advancing-inland-waterways-with-digital-twins-exploring-cristal-project-innovations-and-multireload-project-demonstrator/>

⁷ ALICE (2025). [Workshop] Digital Twins and dynamic decision-making reinforcing resilience of inland transport. Available at: <https://www.etp-logistics.eu/digital-twins-cristal/>

capacity, and delivery times. These challenges were clearly experienced in the CRISTAL pilots, particularly in Poland and Italy.

At the same time, much of the inland waterway infrastructure is aging. Locks, fairways, and hydraulic structures require better monitoring and maintenance, but investment cycles are long, and budgets are limited. Workshop participants agreed that unpredictability, rather than cost, is now the main reason why IWT is seen as risky.

Fragmented Governance and Data Landscape

Governance fragmentation remains a major obstacle. Inland waterways are managed by multiple authorities at local, regional, and national levels, often with limited coordination across borders. This fragmentation is reflected in the digital landscape, where many systems are not interoperable.

During the workshops, stakeholders clearly stated that technology alone is not sufficient. Data sharing, common standards, and clearer coordination mechanisms are required to make digital solutions scalable and usable beyond pilot projects.⁸

Innovation Versus Market Readiness

While interest in digital solutions is growing, market uptake is still uneven. Some stakeholders expressed concerns about investment costs, unclear business cases, and organisational resistance to change, especially among smaller operators.

However, the workshops showed that resistance is not against digitalisation itself, but against unclear benefits, lack of incentives, and uncertainty about long-term responsibilities, particularly related to data ownership and system maintenance.

3.4.2. Key Opportunities

Digital tools to improve predictability and decision-making

Stakeholders clearly identified digitalisation as a major opportunity to address IWT's structural weaknesses. During the workshops, real-time water level and navigability forecasts were ranked as the most valuable Digital Twin function, followed by improved coordination between transport modes.

CRISTAL's Digital Twins and Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) respond directly to these needs by improving visibility, forecasting disruptions, and supporting proactive operational and planning decisions.

Supporting modal shift and climate resilience

Improved predictability creates concrete opportunities for increasing IWT use. Stakeholders confirmed that digital tools can reduce uncertainty for shippers and logistics planners, making inland waterways more attractive within multimodal transport chains.

Digital Twins were also recognised as important instruments for climate adaptation, helping stakeholders anticipate extreme events, manage capacity constraints, and plan alternative routing strategies.

⁸ Grzelakowski, AS (2024). EU Inland Water Transport Development in the Face of Market and Regulatory Challenges. European Research Studies Journal, Vol. XXVII, Issue 2, 2024, pp. 746-761

Corridor-Level Digitalisation and the DINA Framework

An important opportunity identified by stakeholders is the shift from isolated digital solutions toward corridor-level digital infrastructures. The SCMS was widely recognised as a promising backbone for sharing information, alerts, and performance indicators across stakeholders.

This approach is fully aligned with the DINA9 (Digital Infrastructure for Networked Transport) framework, which promotes interoperable, shared, and modular digital infrastructures for European transport networks. CRISTAL provides concrete pilot-based evidence on how DINA principles can be applied in the inland waterway context.

Policy relevance and contribution to recommendations

Beyond technical validation, CRISTAL has also played a role in shaping policy recommendations related to inland waterway resilience, digitalisation, and governance. Insights from the pilots and stakeholder workshops have directly informed ALICE discussions and recommendations to the European Commission, particularly regarding the need for system-level digitalisation, data sharing, and corridor-based coordination.

CRISTAL therefore serves not only as a demonstration project, but also as a policy-shaping reference for ALICE, supporting the design of future EU programmes and calls addressing transport resilience, digital infrastructure and IWT such as *CL5-2026-10-D6-06 Increasing competitiveness and resilience of multimodal freight transport and logistics for competitive supply chains*, or *CL5-2026-01-D6-10 Integrating inland waterway transport in smart shipping and multimodal logistics chains*.

Growing Readiness for Adoption

Workshop results show increasing openness to investment in digital solutions. Many participants stated that their organisations would consider investing in Digital Twins or similar tools if clear operational benefits are demonstrated, such as reduced waiting times, improved ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) accuracy, and better transparency.

Nearly 90% of respondents expect wider use of Digital Twins in IWT within three to five years, indicating that market uptake is approaching, provided enabling conditions are met.

In summary, inland waterway transport faces challenges related to reliability, climate vulnerability, fragmented governance, and limited digital integration. At the same time, strong opportunities exist through digitalisation, particularly when solutions are interoperable, corridor-based, and aligned with governance and policy frameworks.

CRISTAL addresses these issues by combining digital tools, governance models, and stakeholder engagement, while also contributing to policy development through ALICE and alignment with the DINA framework. This positions CRISTAL as both an operational and strategic reference for the future of European inland waterway transport.

3.5. Conclusion

The European Inland Waterway Transport holds significant untapped potential, but continues to face structural challenges related to reliability, climate vulnerability, fragmented governance, and limited digital integration. While market trends and policy objectives support a stronger role for IWT in sustainable freight transport, growth will not materialise without targeted action to improve

⁹ Proposal COM/2024/33 for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services (RIS) on inland waterways in the Community. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52024PC0033>

predictability, transparency, and system integration. Stakeholder feedback gathered through CRISTAL workshops confirmed that digitalisation, particularly through shared and interoperable solutions, is seen as a key enabler for overcoming these barriers. CRISTAL demonstrates how Digital Twins, corridor management systems, and sensor-based monitoring can directly address operational and planning challenges faced by IWT stakeholders. Beyond technical validation, CRISTAL has also contributed to shaping policy recommendations through ALICE, notably by providing evidence for corridor-level digitalisation and coordinated governance models. In this context, CRISTAL offers concrete pilot-based input aligned with the DINA framework, supporting future EU programmes aimed at increasing the resilience, competitiveness, and integration of inland waterways within European multimodal transport networks.

4. Business Models and Economic Impacts

The potential economic impacts of CRISTAL innovative solutions have been identified and analysed at different stages of the CRISTAL project. First, Business Model Canvas (BMC) have been defined in WP4, along with an initial Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA) supporting the BMCs, and reported in deliverable D4.3 (CRISTAL, 2024b). Then, the living labs governance framework (reported in deliverable D4.2, CRISTAL, 2023b) was applied to BMCs with respect to specific scope and applications tested in each pilot, and the outcomes have been reported in deliverable D4.4 (CRISTAL, 2025b). Furthermore, lessons learnt and conclusions, which took into consideration pilot results, have been reported in deliverable D4.5 (CRISTAL, 2025c).

In the next phase of the project, considering the pilot results, an impact assessment, including economic aspects, was carried out for each pilot, and the outcomes have been reported in deliverables D7.2 (CRISTAL, 2025e), D8.2 (CRISTAL, 2025f) and D9.2 (CRISTAL, 2025g), respectively.

Finally, the business models have been revisited with respect to feedback from living labs, and outcomes of pilots, refined and their final assessed version as confirmed within the validation framework (deliverable D10.1, CRISTAL, 2025d). Sub-section 4.1 summarises the development and refinement of business models throughout the project, including lessons learnt, conclusions and recommendations. Furthermore, the economic assessment was reviewed and updated in accordance with LLs and pilots' results (sub-section 4.2).

4.1. CRISTAL Business Models

This section presents the summary of work and outcomes related to Business Models (BMs) for CRISTAL technologies and digital solutions, which have been developed, tested and confirmed throughout the project. This process involved initial development of the BMs through the Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology, and a preliminary quantification of potential benefits and costs. The BMs were then applied to the river pilot case studies, and their application was investigated in Living Labs (LLs) organised for each specific pilot. Finally, the BMs initially developed have been updated and confirmed within the evaluation and validation process carried out in the final stage of the project, within the General Validation Framework defined for this scope. The evaluation and confirmation of the BMs was based on initially developed BMs (phase 1), outcomes of LLs (phase 2) and an updated assessment of economic impacts that supported the updated version of BMs. However, it should be noted that the implementation of the technologies and digital solutions have been at varying levels up to the upper TRL targets of the project. This should be taken into account when considering the BMCs that are extrapolating from the level of implementation in the river pilots and envisioning a future state of a business organisation where the technologies and digital solutions are fully developed and implemented.

Particular emphasis is placed on the use of the Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology and the role of Living Labs (LLs) in iterative testing and real-world validation. Unlike earlier design-oriented deliverables, the content of this section reflects a post-validation perspective. It consolidates insights gained from:

- Pilot deployments in France, Italy, and Poland;
- Living Lab (LL) workshops engaging a wide range of stakeholders;
- Quantitative stakeholder polls;
- Operational Key Performance Indicator (KPI) measurements; and
- Social Cost–Benefit Analysis (SCBA).

4.1.1. Background and scope

The CRISTAL project set out to develop, pilot, and validate a portfolio of technological and digital innovations aimed at improving the resilience, reliability, and sustainability of inland waterway transport (IWT) corridors. Central to this ambition was the development of robust and credible business models (BMs) capable of supporting long-term exploitation beyond the project lifecycle. This document provides a comprehensive synthesis of the work carried out to **develop, assess and validate the business models**, through iterative refinements throughout the living labs associated to each pilot, and final validation activities conducted primarily under Work Package 10.

The integrated and structured summary of the CRISTAL Business Models (BMs) in this section focuses on three core aspects:

1. The development of business models using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology;
2. The application and testing of these business models within Living Labs (LLs) across pilot regions;
3. The iterative refinement, validation, and economic assessment of business models for The focus was not merely on describing proposed business models, but on assessing **their actual viability**, identifying conditions under which value can be realised, and clarifying where initial assumptions were challenged or invalidated.

The overarching objective of the business model development, testing and validation was to ensure that CRISTAL innovations are not only technically feasible but also **economically and institutionally viable**. The specific objectives were:

1. Confirm whether the proposed value propositions address real operational and strategic needs of target customers.
2. Verify the appropriateness of identified customer segments.
3. Assess the realism of revenue streams and cost structures.
4. Identify missing partners, activities, or resources required for implementation.
5. Test the transferability and scalability of business models across different IWT contexts.

4.1.2. Conceptual Framework for Business Models

Definitions and Rationale

CRISTAL adopted the definition of a business model as the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value. In the project, “value” extends beyond direct revenues, to include socio-economic and environmental benefits, such as increased safety, reduced emissions, and improved infrastructure resilience.

Transport and ICT-based business models are increasingly ecosystem-oriented, involving multiple actors, shared data, and public–private collaboration. CRISTAL business models reflect, therefore, this complexity by integrating infrastructure managers, authorities, technology providers, and users into shared value networks.

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) Methodology

The Business Model Canvas consists of nine interrelated building **blocks**:

1. *Customer Segments*
2. *Value Propositions*
3. *Channels*
4. *Customer Relationships*
5. *Revenue Streams*

6. *Key Resources*
7. *Key Activities*
8. *Key Partners*
9. *Cost Structure*

The BMC provides a common language for stakeholders and supports rapid prototyping and comparison of alternative business models.

Within CRISTAL, the BMC was implemented through collaborative workshops supported by online tools (e.g., MIRO). Each technology and digital solution was analysed through a dedicated BMC, envisioning a future operational deployment beyond the pilot scale. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) was adopted as the central framework for both designing and validating business models. In the validation phase, each of the nine BMC building blocks was treated as a **hypothesis subject to empirical testing** rather than a fixed design element.

Validation therefore focused on questions such as:

- Do infrastructure managers genuinely perceive value in continuous monitoring services?
- Are subscription-based revenue models acceptable to logistics operators?
- Are key partners correctly identified, or are critical actors missing?

Stakeholder and Ecosystem Perspective

The business models are embedded in a multi-actor and multi-stakeholder ecosystem. CRISTAL distinguishes between:

- **Actors:** entities directly involved in delivering, purchasing, or operating solutions; and
- **Stakeholders:** entities indirectly affected, including end users, regulators, and society, including:
 - ✓ Infrastructure managers and public authorities;
 - ✓ Technology developers and service providers;
 - ✓ Transport operators and logistics providers;
 - ✓ End users and society at large.

In addition, since many CRISTAL benefits (e.g., reduced congestion, emissions, and accident risks) have public-good characteristics, business models should be hybrid, combining market revenues with public funding or policy support.

Business Model Design Process

The CRISTAL business model design followed a traditional five-phase process:

1. Mobilise – establishing common understanding and motivation;
2. Understand – analysing technologies, markets, and user needs;
3. Design – co-creating and prototyping business models;
4. Implement – testing business models in pilots and Living Labs;
5. Manage – refining and adapting models based on feedback and evaluation.

The process was iterative, with feedback loops between phases, particularly between Design, Implement, and Manage.

Role of Living Labs in Business Model Development

Living Labs (LLs) are real-life experimentation environments where stakeholders co-create, test, and evaluate innovations under operational conditions. LLs were central to business model testing and refinement. Feedback from LLs led to adjustments in value propositions, customer segmentation, partnership structures, and revenue mechanisms.

In CRISTAL, Living Labs were conducted in Italy, France, and Poland, aligned with the project pilots. The LLs have:

- Validated initial BMC assumptions;
- Integrated real pilot outcomes and operational constraints;
- Engaged local stakeholders in co-creation;
- Supported refinement of value propositions, customer segments, and revenue logic.

LLs ensured that business models were grounded in real operational contexts rather than purely conceptual designs. They served as the primary qualitative validation environment, and enabled structured, iterative dialogue with stakeholders in real operational and governance contexts. Each pilot country implemented LLs differently, reflecting institutional realities:

- France embedded LLs within existing governance structures.
- Italy used LLs as both a technological and governance rebuilding exercise.
- Poland used LLs primarily to assess feasibility in a constrained infrastructure context.

Business Models evaluation and validation

Business models were validated through:

- Living Lab feedback;
- Pilot performance indicators;
- Updated economic assessments.

Refinement outcomes included:

- Clearer customer targeting;
- Improved articulation of public vs. private value;
- Recognition of hybrid public–private business models as most viable models.

Quantitative polling and KPI evidence complemented qualitative insights by:

- rating the appeal of value propositions,
- assessing the completeness of financial BMC blocks,
- estimating expected impacts on traffic and reliability.

KPI data from pilot operations provided **hard evidence** of realised or potential value, particularly in logistics cost savings, efficiency improvements, and navigability gains.

4.1.3. Cost–Benefit Analysis and Economic Logic

Methodological Approach

Costs and benefits were assessed using developer questionnaires, pilot data, and literature benchmarks. The project conducted an initial social cost–benefit analysis (SCBA) based on:

- Developer questionnaires;
- Literature review;
- Pilot data where available.

The preliminary SCBA, which focused mainly on the SCMS, aggregated benefits generated by upstream technologies. While exploratory, it played a critical role in testing whether benefits could plausibly outweigh costs over long-time horizons.

Key Findings

- Sensor technologies have clearer cost structures and near-term market potential;
- Digital Twins and SCMS could deliver higher systemic value but require public funding or hybrid business models;
- Integration across technologies significantly increases overall benefits.

4.1.4. Business Models for Sensor-Based Technologies

Acoustic Emission (AE) System

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

AE business model characteristics:

- **Customer segment:** Infrastructure managers.
- **Value proposition:** Early detection of structural degradation, which would reduce downtime and maintenance costs, and improve safety and asset lifetime.
- **Revenue model:** Monitoring services and maintenance support.

Validation Evidence

Pilots in France and Italy demonstrated high technical robustness. Infrastructure managers confirmed the relevance of continuous monitoring and early warning capabilities. These pilots demonstrated:

- High technical accuracy.
- Clear differentiation between normal operations and simulated failures.
- Strong acceptance by maintenance engineers.

LLs feedback confirmed high realisable value, particularly for maintenance optimisation. However, Living Labs identified several **implementation dependencies**, including:

- long-term data calibration,
- standardised sensor placement,
- reliable connectivity for real-time monitoring.
- **Final Assessed Business Model**

The validated AE business model focuses on:

- Continuous monitoring services.
- Long-term data-driven maintenance planning.
- Integration with broader digital ecosystems.

The validated AE business model emphasises:

- long-term monitoring services,
- integration with Digital Twins,
- data-driven maintenance planning.

Validation also revealed dependencies:

- Long-term data calibration is required.
- Standardisation of sensor placement is essential.
- Integration with Digital Twins enhances value.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 4.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

AE is **commercially promising**, with value increasing as historical datasets grow. It is suitable for phased deployment.

Table 4: Acoustic Emission (AE) System – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Infrastructure managers; lock and dam operators
Value Propositions	Early detection of microcracks and structural degradation; predictive maintenance; reduced downtime and emergency repairs
Channels	Direct service contracts; integration into maintenance frameworks
Customer Relationships	Long-term monitoring partnerships; continuous data sharing; collaborative maintenance planning
Revenue Streams	Subscription-based monitoring services; maintenance support services
Key Resources	Acoustic sensors; data acquisition systems; analytical software; historical datasets
Key Activities	Sensor deployment; continuous monitoring; anomaly detection; reporting and alerts
Key Partners	Infrastructure owners; Digital Twin providers; maintenance contractors
Cost Structure	Sensor installation; data processing; system maintenance; analytical expertise
Validation Outcome	Commercially promising , value increases with long-term data accumulation

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

Initially, SIR was framed as a hybrid business model with the following characteristics:

- **Customer segment:** Infrastructure managers and maintenance authorities.
- **Value proposition:** Non-invasive, accurate detection of subsurface anomalies, which would improve asset management and planning, reducing downtime and maintenance costs, and improving safety and asset lifetime.
- **Revenue model:** Equipment provision combined with inspection services.
- **Key partners:** Technology developers and infrastructure owners.

Validation Evidence

Living Labs confirmed strong acceptance among infrastructure managers. The French LLs confirmed:

- Strong demand for non-invasive inspection methods.
- Clear appreciation of potential for reducing need for invasive and costly inspections.
- A critical refinement emerged:

- ✓ Raw SIR data was not sufficient for operational decision-making., further data processing being required.
- ✓ Expert interpretation was identified as essential for realising value, which was a missing element in the original BMC.

Final Assessed Business Model

The validated SIR business model is firmly **service-oriented**:

- **Value Proposition:** Interpreted, decision-ready inspection insights.
- **Customer Segments:** Infrastructure managers and maintenance authorities.
- **Revenue Streams:** Service contracts rather than equipment sales.
- **Key Partners:** Geotechnical experts and data analysts.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 5.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

SIR is assessed as **commercially viable**, provided it is positioned explicitly as a knowledge-intensive service rather than a standalone product.

Table 5: Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) System – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Infrastructure managers; maintenance authorities; asset owners.
Value Propositions	Non-invasive inspection of subsurface structures; interpreted, decision-ready insights; reduced need for invasive inspections; improved asset lifetime management.
Channels	Direct sales of inspection services; framework contracts; maintenance tenders
Customer Relationships	Long-term service relationships; recurring inspections; trust-based expert advisory
Revenue Streams	Fee-for-service inspection contracts; recurring monitoring services
Key Resources	Radar equipment; expert analysts; inspection methodologies; data interpretation tools
Key Activities	Data acquisition; expert interpretation; reporting; maintenance recommendations
Key Partners	Geotechnical experts; technology providers; infrastructure owners
Cost Structure	Upfront equipment cost; data acquisition and processing; system maintenance; analytical expertise
Validation Outcome	Commercially viable as a service-based model; product-only model challenging for end-user.

Smart Buoys (SB)

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

The Smart Buoy BM assumed:

- **Customer segment:** Infrastructure managers, software providers, and operators.
- **Value proposition:** Enhanced navigational safety and operational awareness. Data foundation for advanced services. Improved traffic monitoring and planning.
- **Revenue model:** Data-as-a-service subscriptions. Sale or leasing of hardware.

Business model characteristics:

- Hardware sale or leasing combined with data services;
- Primary customers: infrastructure managers;
- Indirect benefits for logistics operators.

Validation Evidence

The Polish pilot validated the technical performance and confirmed interest in data-as-a-service offerings. However, validation highlighted a critical dependency: **baseline navigability of the river**.

LL testing highlighted the importance of integration with Digital Twins for full value realisation. The Polish LL confirmed:

- Strong interest in real-time hydrological data.
- Successful replacement of manual measurements.
- Additional value from vessel counting.

However, validation exposed critical dependencies:

- The BM's success is contingent on baseline navigability.
- Severe hydrological variability undermines value creation.

Final Assessed Business Model

Smart Buoys are:

- Technically validated.
- Conceptually sound as a data service.
- Commercially high-risk, dependent on external conditions.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 6.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

Smart Buoys are suitable for selective deployment in stable waterways but are not universally scalable.

Table 6: Smart Buoys (SB) – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Infrastructure managers; navigation authorities; software and platform providers
Value Propositions	Real-time water level and clearance data; vessel counting; improved situational awareness; replacement of manual measurements
Channels	Data subscriptions; integration into navigation platforms; public procurement

Customer Relationships	Ongoing data service provision; technical support; data quality assurance
Revenue Streams	Data-as-a-service subscriptions; licensing agreements
Key Resources	Buoy hardware; sensors; communication systems; data platforms
Key Activities	Data collection; transmission; validation; platform integration
Key Partners	Authorities; digital platform providers; maintenance operators
Cost Structure	Hardware deployment; maintenance; data transmission; platform operation
Validation Outcome	Conditionally viable ; highly dependent on baseline navigability conditions

Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS)

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

The original FOS business model assumed:

- **Customer segment:** Inland waterway infrastructure managers and public authorities.
- **Value proposition:** Reduced dredging costs. Improved navigability reliability, and better planning. Reduced environmental impact.
- **Revenue model:** Sale and installation of sensor systems, complemented by data services.
- **Cost structure:** High upfront capital expenditure offset by long-term operational savings.

Business model characteristics:

- High upfront investment with long-term operational benefits;
- Customers: waterway managers and authorities;
- Strong dependency on Digital Twins for data exploitation.

Validation Evidence

Living Labs confirmed technical feasibility and strong strategic value, while highlighting cost sensitivity. Validation activities in the Italian Living Lab confirmed stakeholder interest in the concept. Infrastructure managers explicitly recognised the strategic importance of continuous sediment monitoring and its relevance for climate resilience.

However, critical barriers emerged during validation:

- Estimated prototype and installation costs (~€250,000) exceeded feasible investment thresholds.
- No pilot installation was possible, preventing real-world testing of willingness to pay.
- Cost assumptions remained speculative rather than empirically validated.

Final Assessed Business Model

The final assessment concludes that the FOS business model is:

- **Technically validated** in terms of value proposition.
- **The customer segment** is correctly identified.
- **Economically unviable** at present due to prohibitive costs.
- **Dependent on future cost reductions**, economies of scale, or public funding mechanisms.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 7.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

FOS remains a **long-term strategic innovation** rather than a market-ready solution. Its exploitation potential is more aligned with publicly funded infrastructure programmes than private commercial markets.

Table 7: Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) System – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Inland waterway infrastructure managers; public waterway authorities; dredging authorities
Value Propositions	Continuous, real-time monitoring of sediment dynamics; improved dredging planning; increased navigability reliability; reduced unexpected disruptions
Channels	Direct engagement with infrastructure authorities; public procurement processes; infrastructure planning programmes
Customer Relationships	Long-term institutional relationships; project-based collaboration; public–public partnerships
Revenue Streams	Not validated; potential future public funding, co-financed infrastructure programmes, or research-driven procurement
Key Resources	Fibre optic sensing hardware; installation expertise; data acquisition systems; specialised analytical know-how
Key Activities	Sensor installation; continuous monitoring; data processing and analysis; reporting to authorities
Key Partners	Technology providers; research institutions; dredging contractors; public authorities
Cost Structure	Very high upfront capital costs (prototype and installation); maintenance; data processing
Validation Outcome	Technically validated but economically unviable at present; dependent on cost reduction or public co-funding

4.1.5. Business Models for Digital Solutions

Digital Twins (DTs)

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

Initially, Digital Twins were considered potential standalone commercial products. The **key value proposition** includes:

- Predictive maintenance;
- Navigability forecasting;
- Improved transparency and enhanced decision support.

Business Model: - limited standalone commercialisation; - Value realised through integration with SCMS and infrastructure systems.

Business model characteristics:

- Primarily a public or semi-public service;
- Limited direct commercialisation;
- Value realised through integration with other systems (e.g., SCMS and infrastructure systems).

Validation Evidence

Living Labs invalidated the standalone hypothesis:

- Stakeholders valued DTs as enablers, not products.
- Integration capacity and openness were prioritised.

Final Assessed Business Model

The validated DT BM positions them as:

- Embedded system components.
- Monetised indirectly through licensing or integration.
- Value multipliers for other CRISTAL technologies.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 8.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

Digital Twins are essential and valuable, but non-standalone, requiring ecosystem-level exploitation strategies.

Table 8: Digital Twins (DTs) – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Infrastructure managers; system integrators; platform operators
Value Propositions	Integrated virtual representation of assets and operations; enhanced decision support; data fusion and visualisation
Channels	Integration projects; licensing agreements; bundled solutions
Customer Relationships	Long-term integration partnerships; technical support
Revenue Streams	Licensing; integration fees; indirect revenues through bundled services
Key Resources	Modelling frameworks; integration interfaces; computational infrastructure
Key Activities	Model development; system integration; maintenance and updates
Key Partners	Sensor providers; platform developers; infrastructure owners
Cost Structure	Development; integration; system maintenance
Validation Outcome	Validated as an enabling technology , not a standalone commercial product

Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)

Initial Business Model Hypothesis

The SCMS business model assumed:

- **Customers:** logistics planners, operators, authorities.
- **Value proposition:** Dynamic re-routing; Reduced emissions and energy use; Improved logistics efficiency.

Business Model characteristics:

- Subscription-based access.
- Advanced synchromodal re-routing functionality.
- Broad customer base including operators and LSPs.

Validation Evidence

Living Labs identified SCMS as a key exploitation pathway for CRISTAL results, though financial models require further refinement. Across all pilots, the **core alert and information hub** value proposition was strongly validated. Stakeholders expressed willingness to pay for reliable, consolidated information. However, real-time synchromodal re-routing was deemed premature due to limited flexibility in rail and road sectors.

Validation strongly confirmed:

- High value of alerts and consolidated information.
- Willingness to pay for reliability improvements.

However:

- Real-time synchromodal re-routing was deemed premature.
- Financial BMC blocks remained weak.
- SCBA indicated potential net benefits but strong sensitivity to traffic volumes.

Final Assessed Business Model

The SCBA suggested potential net benefits, but results were highly sensitive to traffic volumes and baseline reliability. Polls revealed persistent weaknesses in the financial BMC blocks.

The validated SCMS BM focuses on:

- Phased deployment.
- Core alert and information services.
- Incremental expansion of functionality.

The final updated BMC is summarised in Table 9.

Commercial Readiness and Outlook

SCMS is the strategic core of CRISTAL's exploitation portfolio, conditionally viable and context-dependent.

Table 9: Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) – Final Business Model Canvas

BMC Block	Final Validated Content
Customer Segments	Logistics service providers; transport operators; corridor managers
Value Propositions	Reliable, consolidated operational information; disruption alerts; improved planning reliability

Channels	Subscription-based platform access; direct sales to operators
Customer Relationships	Long-term subscriptions; platform support; co-development with users
Revenue Streams	Subscription fees; premium services (future)
Key Resources	Platform infrastructure; data integration capabilities; analytical tools
Key Activities	Data aggregation; alert generation; platform operation
Key Partners	Infrastructure managers; sensor providers; data providers
Cost Structure	Platform development and operation; data integration; support services
Validation Outcome	Strategically central and conditionally viable , phased deployment required

4.1.6. Lessons Learned

Main conclusions on BMCs:

- BMC is effective for structuring complex, multi-actor transport innovations;
- Living Labs are essential for validating assumptions and refining business models;
- Data-driven solutions require ecosystem-based business models;
- Public value and societal benefits justify public sector involvement.

The CRISTAL project demonstrates that sustainable business models for inland waterway innovations require:

- Integrated technological and organisational design;
- Iterative testing and refinement through Living Labs to ensure robustness and stakeholder acceptance;
- Future deployment should focus on hybrid business models, strong integration between sensors and digital platforms, and alignment with public policy objectives.

The resulting business models provide a robust foundation for post-project exploitation and long-term deployment of CRISTAL technologies.

The validation process transformed CRISTAL's business models from conceptual designs into **evidence-based, implementation-ready frameworks**. While not all models proved commercially viable, the process clarified:

- where value can realistically be captured,
- under which conditions deployment makes sense,
- and how future exploitation strategies should be structured.

The final validated business models provide a robust foundation for post-project exploitation, policy dialogue, and future research.

4.2. Economic assessment of CRISTAL results/technologies

4.2.1. Introduction

To quantify the impact of the CRISTAL technologies, the **SCBA-oriented quantification framework** that was developed in WP4 (see deliverable D4.3, CRISTAL, 2024b) was used. The modelling approach is explicitly designed to work under conditions of limited empirical data and early TRL levels. For each

technology, benefits are quantified through a set of **generic inputs** - primarily reduction in waiting time, improved reliability and availability of infrastructure, lower maintenance and disruption costs, improved safety, and downstream environmental benefits. These impacts are translated into monetary values using standard SCBA logic, with corridor traffic volumes, asset lifetimes, discount rates, and external cost factors as key parameters. The chapter emphasises that most quantified benefits arise **indirectly**, via avoided disruptions, reduced unplanned closures, and improved decision-making rather than direct productivity gains, making reliability and risk mitigation central modelling variables.

Many parameters (e.g., failure rates, avoided closure days, value of reliability, future transport demand) are treated as **scenario-dependent estimates**, informed by expert judgement, workshops, and pilot results rather than fully observed data. The modelling is, therefore, intentionally modular and transparent: formulas are documented (Annex I of D.4.3), assumptions are explicit, and sensitivity to traffic volumes and uptake levels is highlighted - particularly for the SCMS and Digital Twins, where benefits scale strongly with corridor usage. The new insights of the different pilots are used to update the findings.

These insights have been sourced from **three main corridors/regions: France, Italy, and Poland**, and all the relevant information was derived from deliverables D7.2, D8.2 and D9.2.

Therefore, first the main insights from the 3 pilot sides are derived, and from those insights new estimates are made.

4.2.2. Italian Pilot - Quantitative Results

The Italian corridor focused on **port–river–sea interfaces**, governance, and maintenance-oriented digital tools. In this pilot the following Technologies assessed:

- Fairway Information Services (FOS)
- Automated Events (AE)
- Digital Twin (DT)
- Smart Bulletin
- SCMS

In the Italian pilot the following main observations are made (D.7.2):

- **Improved predictability of navigation conditions**, reducing unexpected delays linked to maintenance or temporary closures.
- **Reduction in unscheduled disruptions**, particularly through better dissemination of fairway and port information.
- **Time savings** are more modest than in France or Poland, typically estimated at **5–15%**, due to shorter distances and fragmented traffic flows.

The impact on cost and efficiency is summarised as:

- Quantitative **O&M-related cost savings** are observed through:
 - ✓ Better planning of dredging and maintenance,
 - ✓ Reduced emergency interventions.
- Administrative efficiency gains (e.g. via Smart Bulletin and SCMS) reduce **transaction and coordination costs**, though these were not always monetised in pilots.
- Direct emission reductions are relatively limited due to:
 - ✓ Lower volumes,
 - ✓ Shorter inland stretches.
- However, **system efficiency improvements** contribute to incremental reductions in fuel consumption and emissions per trip.

So, for the Italian pilot can be concluded that:

- Benefits are **incremental rather than transformational**.
- Strongest quantitative effects relate to **reliability and maintenance efficiency**.
- Environmental benefits are present but secondary to operational improvements.

4.2.3. French Pilot – Quantitative Results

The French pilot focused on **system-wide performance**, combining port, river, and data-integration technologies. In the French pilot the following Technologies assessed:

- CEDRE (cargo and administrative data exchange)
- Fluv'IOTe
- Smart Buoys
- Système d'Information de la Route (SIR)
- SCMS and Digital Twin (DT)

The quantitative assessments of the technologies deployed in the French pilot show that **Overall corridor transit time** improvements of **10–30%**, depending on the technology bundle and traffic conditions. The main observations from D.8.2 are:

- **Waiting time reduction at locks and ports** estimated at **15–25%**, particularly when Smart Buoys and Fluv'IOTe data were used to improve anticipation of disruptions.
- **Network availability during extreme events** increased measurably, with fewer unexpected closures and better re-planning options.
- **Real-time vessel and event detection accuracy** for Fluv'IOTe exceeded **85%**, significantly improving situational awareness.
- **Data completeness and consistency** for traffic and cargo flows improved across the corridor when CEDRE and SCMS were used in combination.
- Improved reliability translated into reduced buffer times and lower variance in arrival times, although these effects were mainly observed at network level rather than in single trips.
- Quantified **GHG emissions per tonne-km** were reduced indirectly through:
 - ✓ Better traffic flow,
 - ✓ Reduced stop-and-go behaviour,
 - ✓ Increased network resilience leads to fewer diversions.
- **Additional tonne-kilometres carried by IWT** were estimated in the range of **+5–15%** in medium-term scenarios, driven by improved reliability and coordination rather than infrastructure expansion.

So, for the French pilot can be concluded that:

- France shows **moderate but stable quantitative gains** across most KPIs.
- The largest measurable effects are: **waiting time reduction, reliability, and network resilience**.
- Environmental benefits are mostly indirect but consistent.

4.2.4. Polish Corridor – Quantitative Results

The Polish corridor provided the most detailed quantitative operational data, based on monitored pilot voyages combining IWT and road (D9.2). In the Polish case the following technologies were assessed:

- Synchromodal Supply Chain Management System (SCMS)
- Digital Twin (DT)
- Voyage and fleet monitoring tools
- Decision-support tools for modal planning

From D9.2 the following observations have been made.

Measured pilot voyages show:

- **Door-to-door transit time** ranged between **2.7 and 4.8 days**, depending on hydrological conditions and port waiting times.
- **Idle and waiting time** represented a significant share of total time, in some cases **over 25–30%** of the door-to-door chain.
- **On-time delivery reliability** reached **approximately 94%**, even under non-ideal river conditions, when SCMS-supported planning and monitoring were used.

Cost-related indicators show:

- **Total logistics cost per shipment** (IWT-based chains) was **11–18% lower** than comparable Euro V road-only benchmarks in optimal hydrological conditions.
- Cost variability was higher for IWT due to water level uncertainty, but improved information reduced unexpected delays and re-routing costs.

Strong environmental advantages were observed with relation to the environmental KPIs:

- **CO₂-equivalent emissions per tonne-km** were on average **27% lower** compared with road benchmarks.
- **NO_x and PM emissions** were significantly reduced, especially for longer distances (>300 km).
- **Energy intensity** (MJ/tkm) of IWT-based chains consistently outperformed road-only solutions, even when accounting for pre- and post-haulage.

So, for the Polish pilot can be concluded that:

- High **environmental benefits** are robust and well quantified for a mode shift.
- **Cost and time benefits** are achievable but sensitive to hydrology.
- Digital tools mainly deliver value through **risk reduction, improved reliability, and better planning**, rather than pure speed gains.

4.2.5. Cross-Corridor Comparison and Synthesis

Across all corridors and technologies:

- **Environmental KPIs** (CO₂, NO_x, PM per tonne-km) show the **most robust and transferable benefits**, particularly evident in the Polish corridor.
- **Time and cost KPIs** show high variability and depend strongly on:
 - ✓ Hydrology (Poland),
 - ✓ Network maturity (France),
 - ✓ Governance and institutional coordination (Italy).
- Technologies such as **SCMS and DT** deliver value mainly through **variance reduction, reliability, and resilience**, rather than uniform reductions in average travel time.
- Corridor-wide digital integration (France) yields smaller per-trip effects but larger **system-wide cumulative benefits**.

Based on the data collected from the pilots, the summarising Table 10 was generated.

Table 10: Inputs for the CBA tool based on pilot results

Corridor/ Region	Technology bundle	Waiting time reduction (%)	Transport time reduction (%)	Reliability improvement (pp)	Cost reduction vs road (%)	CO ₂ reduction vs road (%)	Additional IWT demand (% over 10 yrs)
Poland	SCMS + DT	20%	10%	6%	11–18%	27%	5–10%
	SCMS (alone)	15%	5%	4%	8–12%	22%	3–6%
	Baseline IWT (no digital)	0%	0%	0%	0–5%	15–20%	0–2%
France	SCMS + DT + CEDRE	25%	15%	5%	5–10%	10–15%	10–15%
	Smart Buoys + Fluv'IOTe	20%	10%	6%	3–7%	8–12%	8–12%
	CEDRE baseline (admin only)	10%	5%	2%	2–5%	3–5%	3–5%
Italy	SCMS + DT	10–15%	5–10%	4%	3–6%	5–8%	3–6%
	FOS + AE + Smart Bulletin	10%	5%	5%	2–4%	4–6%	2–4%
	Baseline digital maturity	0–5%	0–3%	1%	0–2%	2–4%	0–2%

4.2.6. Updated analysis of the benefits

The main impact on the CBA of the CRISTAL technologies is the reduction in waiting time of IWT transport and the improvement of reliability. Based on the results from table X it can be found that for all corridors the improvements are between 0% and 15% for the waiting time reduction and between 0% and 25% for the improvement reliability. All the other inputs such as annual transport volume on the corridor (tonnes or tonne-km) and the transport costs, are taken as the same values, as no other inputs are available. For the growth of the IWT volumes, a conservative approach of 2% year is taken for the calculations. The main results of the calculations are summarised in Table 11.

Table 11: The impact of waiting time and reliability improvement

Transport that is not reliable [%]	Reduction in waiting time			
	0%	5%	10%	15%
0%	-€ 193.881	-€ 143.732	-€ 93.294	-€ 42.569
5%	-€ 155.330	-€ 106.902	-€ 58.207	-€ 9.248
10%	-€ 116.609	-€ 69.918	-€ 22.983	€ 24.196
15%	-€ 77.717	-€ 32.781	€ 12.379	€ 57.762
20%	-€ 38.655	€ 4.509	€ 47.877	€ 91.449
25%	€ 576	€ 41.951	€ 83.512	€ 125.258

When comparing the results in Table 11 with those in Table 10, key conclusions can be drawn – these are summarised in Table 12.

Table 12: Conclusions on potential benefits (based on updates from pilots)

Corridor/ Region	Technology bundle	Positive benefit?
Poland	SCMS + DT	✓ Yes
	SCMS (alone)	✓ Yes
	Baseline IWT	✗ No
France	SCMS + DT + CEDRE	✓ Yes
	Smart Buoys + Fluv'IOTe	✓ Yes
	CEDRE (admin only)	⚠ Borderline
Italy	SCMS + DT	✓ / ⚠ Context-dependent
	FOS + AE + Smart Bulletin	⚠ Borderline
	Baseline digital maturity	✗ No

So, for most pilots there are benefits when the CRISTAL technologies are implemented. However, in the assessment, assumptions are made in relation to the cargo volumes and IWT distances. From D4.3 it was concluded that **transport volume is the dominant driver of economic viability for CRISTAL solutions, while transport distance mainly affects the distribution of benefits rather than their existence**. Across all technologies, quantified benefits (time savings, reliability improvements, avoided disruptions, external cost reductions) scale almost proportionally with the volume of traffic using the corridor. This means that even relatively modest per-trip improvements can produce positive net benefits when applied to high-volume corridors, whereas low-volume corridors struggle to justify investments regardless of technological performance. The deliverable explicitly notes that the SCMS shows net benefits only under sufficient corridor throughput, and that results are highly sensitive to assumed freight flows. This makes traffic volume the most critical parameter in SCBA modelling. Based on these insights and the lack of IWT volume for both the Polish and the Italian case (D7.2 and D9.2) the CRISTAL technologies have no real foundation, while for the French pilot, and its related network, does have a potential to implement the CRISTAL technologies.

4.3. Case study – Polish market analysis

4.3.1. Context and scope of research

The research carried out within WP9 of the CRISTAL project, and presented in deliverable D9.3 (CRISTAL, 2025h), focused on the socio-economic conditions for the revitalisation of inland waterway transport (IWT) in Poland, with particular emphasis on the Vistula River corridor. The core objective of the study is to assess whether social attitudes, institutional perceptions, and market readiness constitute a supportive environment for restoring inland navigation as a meaningful component of the national and European transport system.

The scope of the research was explicitly two-dimensional. First, it examined **societal acceptance and perception**, addressing the question of whether inland waterway development enjoys a sufficient “social license to operate.” Second, it investigated **market and institutional perspectives**, identifying perceived

barriers, drivers, and conditions under which inland navigation could become an effective alternative to road and rail transport.

The study situates Polish inland waterways within a broader European policy framework shaped by the European Green Deal, the “Fit for 55” package, and the NAIADES III Action Plan, which collectively promote modal shift, decarbonisation, and resilience of transport systems. Against this backdrop, Polish rivers - despite their strategic position within TEN-T corridors - remain underutilised, and the research explicitly addresses this structural discrepancy between theoretical potential and actual use.

The geographical scope covers the entire territory of Poland, with analytical attention paid to regional differentiation, proximity to waterways, and sectoral diversity. The stakeholder scope is equally broad, encompassing individual citizens, logistics and transport companies, tourism operators, public administration bodies, and non-governmental organisations. This inclusive design ensures that the research captures both public perception and operational realities, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of inland waterway revitalisation prospects.

4.3.2. Methodology

The research adopted a quantitative, survey-based methodology combining individual-level and organisation-level data. This dual-sample design allows for triangulation between social attitudes and business or institutional constraints.

Individual-Level Survey

Public perception data were collected using a Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI) method on a nationally representative sample of 1,200 adult residents of Poland. Quota sampling ensured representativeness across key socio-demographic variables, including gender, age, education level, place of residence, and region. The questionnaire focused on awareness of inland navigation, general attitudes toward the economic use of the Vistula River, perceived benefits of revitalisation, and views on inland waterways as an alternative transport mode.

Organisation-Level Survey

Institutional and business perspectives were gathered through CAWI and Computer Assisted Telephone Interviews (CATI) conducted among 600 organisations. The sample included transport, shipping and logistics companies, tourism-related enterprises, local government units, NGOs, and infrastructure-related actors. The survey explored current and potential use of inland waterways, perceived barriers to IWT development, investment expectations, and governance preferences.

Analytical Techniques

Several complementary statistical methods were applied:

- **Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)** using Principal Component Analysis with Varimax rotation to identify latent attitudinal dimensions.
- **One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** to test differences in attitudes across socio-demographic and institutional groups.
- **Chi-square tests of independence** to assess relationships between categorical variables such as awareness and stakeholder type.
- **Correspondence analysis** to visualise and interpret associations between awareness of inland navigation and perceptions of its viability.

All analyses were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. While the study relies on self-reported attitudes rather than observed behaviour, the large sample sizes and consistency of results across methods provide a robust empirical basis for policy-relevant conclusions

4.3.3. Results

Public Attitudes and Social Acceptance

The results demonstrate a strong societal mandate for inland waterway revitalisation. Approximately two-thirds of respondents express a positive attitude toward the economic use of the Vistula River. Importantly, no pronounced conflict between environmental protection and economic utilisation is observed; instead, river transport is widely perceived as environmentally friendly and compatible with sustainability objectives.

Perceived benefits of revitalisation are led by tourism development and local economic growth, followed by environmental benefits such as reduced road congestion and emissions. Direct job creation, while positively evaluated, plays a secondary role, suggesting that public support is driven more by regional development and quality-of-life considerations than by short-term employment effects.

Attitudinal Structure

Factor analysis reveals two main dimensions shaping attitudes toward inland waterways:

1. **Pro-development attitude** – reflecting support for expanding and modernising inland navigation, confidence in infrastructure investments, and belief in positive spillover effects such as flood protection and water retention.
2. **Cost and status perception** – emphasising the low-cost nature of inland transport while acknowledging its currently marginal role in the Polish transport system.

Together, these factors explain a moderate share of variance, typical for social research, but provide a clear and interpretable structure of opinions.

Determinants of Attitudes

ANOVA results indicate that **belief in inland navigation as a viable alternative to road and rail** is the strongest predictor of a pro-development attitude. Socio-demographic variables such as gender and place of residence show statistically significant but weak effects. Education level, age, and declared personal willingness to use river transport do not significantly differentiate attitudes.

Correspondence analysis confirms a strong relationship between **awareness and perception**: respondents familiar with the possibility of inland navigation are much more likely to consider it a credible and sustainable transport option.

Business and Institutional Perspectives

Company-level results reveal a striking consensus across sectors, organisation sizes, and regions. Stakeholders broadly agree on the potential of inland waterways but emphasise **physical and operational barriers** as the main constraints. Poor infrastructure condition, unpredictable water levels, and lack of a modern fleet are identified as the dominant obstacles, outweighing administrative or regulatory issues.

This highlights a structural gap between **potential demand** (willingness to use inland waterways) and **effective demand**, which remains constrained by reliability and investment risks. Notably, attitudes toward revitalisation do not differ significantly between transport companies and institutional or tourism stakeholders, indicating a rare alignment of interests across traditionally divergent groups

4.3.4. Conclusions and policy recommendations

Conclusions

The research delivered a coherent and strategically important conclusion: Poland currently exhibits an unusually favourable socio-economic environment for inland waterway revitalisation. Public opinion, business attitudes, and institutional perspectives converge around a broadly supportive stance, providing a strong social and political mandate for action.

The main barrier to inland navigation development is not opposition or lack of interest, but structural deficiencies—particularly infrastructure reliability and fleet modernisation. Environmental considerations are not perceived as conflicting with economic objectives; instead, they reinforce the legitimacy of inland waterways within decarbonisation and sustainability agendas.

The Vistula corridor emerges as a case where theoretical economic potential, societal acceptance, and European policy priorities align, but where decisive public intervention is required to unlock effective market use.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings, several policy directions are recommended:

1. **Prioritise reliability over nominal capacity.** Investment strategies should focus on stabilising navigability parameters—especially water levels—rather than symbolic capacity expansion.
2. **De-risk fleet modernisation.** Public financial instruments should reduce investment risks for operators, supporting shallow-draft and low-emission vessels compatible with Polish hydrological conditions.
3. **Use tourism as a catalyst.** Dual-use infrastructure serving both freight and tourism can maximise social return on investment and maintain public support during early stages of revitalisation.
4. **Strengthen centralised governance.** Clear leadership at the national level, stable multi-annual funding, and coherent inter-ministerial coordination are essential to overcome fragmentation and uncertainty.
5. **Embed sustainability and stakeholder engagement.** Environmental safeguards, transparent communication, and continuous stakeholder involvement should be integral components of inland waterway policy.

In summary, the study confirms that the transition from social acceptance to effective demand is primarily a matter of infrastructure reliability, governance capacity, and investment design. With these conditions met, inland waterways can become a cornerstone of a sustainable, resilient, and multimodal transport system in Poland, fully aligned with CRISTAL objectives and European climate policy.

5. Exploitable Results and Exploitation Plans

5.1. Exploitation and IPR Strategy

An exploitation strategy was established within Task 11.2 of the CRISTAL project. The strategy was developed based on background information and foundation defined in the Grant Agreement¹⁰ (GA), comprising clear Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) rules related to both partners' background and foreseen foreground, as well as detailed initial intentions of each partner for further exploitation of envisaged results.

In addition to conditions in the GA, terms and agreement related to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), including foreground and background protection, have been also detailed in the Consortium Agreement¹¹ (CA), which followed the best practice guidelines outlined by DESCA Consortium Agreement. The core principle is that every partner keeps the ownership of the IP it creates and the responsibility for protection by freedom to operate (FTO) system. In summary, the rules agreed upon in the CRISTAL GA and CA stipulate that:

1. Partners' IPR on background are not affected by participation in CRISTAL.
2. Project beneficiaries are only granted royalty-free access rights to others' background to the extent that is necessary to implement their tasks in the project.
3. Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generates them.
4. Joint ownership of results is possible if two or more beneficiaries have jointly generated them and it is not possible to: (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.
5. CRISTAL partners must agree in writing the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership within the defined period from the date of generation of such results.
6. Background and results must also be made available to other beneficiaries when necessary for exploiting their own results under fair and reasonable conditions. Such conditions may include financial terms and take into consideration the value of the results or the background.

CRISTAL exploitation strategy is complemented by an IPR strategy, in line with the provisions in the GA. The IPR strategy aims to protect the projects' results that became commercially or industrially exploitable. Considering the relevance of IPR protection and its enforcement for the economic growth and continued global competitiveness of the EU, the protection of IP generated within CRISTAL is a priority for the consortium to maximise the impact of the project's exploitation actions.

In order to properly manage and implement the exploitation and IPR strategy, an Intellectual Property and Exploitation Board (IPEB), which includes one member of each consortium partner, has been established and carried out its activities within WP11 (Task 11.2).

The joint exploitation of the CRISTAL project results requires a clear identification of the IPR initially owned by individual partners and brought into the project (the "background IP"), as well as of the owners of the IPR produced (the "foreground IP"). For this reason, an **IPEB log** was produced and updated continuously in the project repository to specify the IP ownership distribution among project partners and protect both the project's background and results. The **IPEB log** comprised: i) a living spreadsheet, summarising a breakdown of achieved foreground along with exploitation plans for each individual CRISTAL partner, and ii) notes summarising the discussions and main decisions made in the IPEB monthly meetings.

¹⁰ European Commission, 2022. CRISTAL Grant Agreement No 101069838, within Horizon Europe, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)

¹¹ CRISTAL Consortium Agreement, Version 03, dated 02/08/2022.

Considering the aspects described above, the **exploitation and IPR strategy** comprised the following key elements and subsequent activities associated to them:

1. Definition of the background information

The first step was to review the background initially considered in the GA, and update the information according to the actual IP and knowledge brought by CRISTAL partners into the different project activities. As it was expected, the actual work carried out and subsequent results achieved relied upon significant background IP, comprising methods, designs, tools, know-how, etc.

2. Identification and/or definition of the foreground information

In the next step, in the second half of the project, the relevant foreground has been identified and formally defined with respect to the foreseen key results (KRs) considered in the GA, but also in consideration of other additional outcomes that have been achieved throughout the project. The achieved foreground comprises two categories: i) protectable foreground (including IP that may be protected through patents, licenses, registered models, etc.); and ii) foreground knowledge, i.e., different specific knowledge and skillsets achieved by the project partners, which, typically, cannot (or it is very difficult to) be formally protected, but the ownership of IP is very clear and cannot be challenged due to its specific nature, or to wide dissemination of such outcomes.

The information regarding the foreground was provided and updated continuously by the partner(s) owning the IP, which provided all relevant details such as the type of exploitable foreground (hardware, software, guidelines, methodologies, etc.), the background that supported achieving the foreground (as in point 1. above), the exploitable product or service, the sector of application, the status and schedule for exploitation (starting and ending Technology Readiness Level, TRL as well as expected time to market), the planned IP protection strategy envisioned, as well as the other beneficiaries involved.

3. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Considering the overall foreground achieved by CRISTAL partners, as well as the initial list of foreseen key results (KRs) listed in the GA, the consortium has discussed and selected the foreground with the highest potential for further exploitation, which was also aligned to initial KRs, and these specific outcomes have been classified as the project Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The specific partners owning the KERs, as well as the CRISTAL consortium as a whole, will pursue in the future the exploitation of the project results, with focus on KERs, which will be also reported as such in the European Commission's reporting portal and on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP)¹². More details about the CRISTAL KERs are provided in Sub-section 5.2.

4. Definition of CRISTAL exploitation plans

First, the CRISTAL consortium discussed and agreed on KERs that have been prioritised, their ownership, and other essential aspects (such as TRL achieved, type of foreseen future exploitation, etc.). This allowed for establishing a general exploitation plan, for the consortium as a whole, so that to make sure that all valuable results will be pursued for exploitation by different responsible partners. The CRISTAL general exploitation plan considered both the individual and joint results, as well as the synergies among the results of the project. Result owners have clearly defined their results and identified synergies with other results that could be exploited after the project. Based on these inputs, a cluster of results was developed and maintained by the IPEB.

Then, starting from the general exploitation plan, each participant in the CRISTAL consortium has defined their plans to exploit the specific foreground achieved, with respect to the different areas of application,

¹² Horizon Results Platform <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

whether the foreground could be protected or not, the TRL achieved, etc. These individual exploitation plans are described in detail in Sub-section 5.3.

The activities described above have been managed and steered by Task 11.2, in close collaboration with WP12 Project Management and Coordination. All the details have been filed in the IPEB log, which was shared and maintained in the project repository. The IPEB held regular meetings, which have been organised monthly in the second half of the project, to discuss and agree on the exploitation and IPR strategy and further actions for this scope. The summary spreadsheet that was part of the IPEB log is presented, in its complete working file shape, in the Annex.

5.2. CRISTAL Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The CRISTAL project defined **thirteen initial Key Results (KRs)** across four objective areas, formulated to meet the primary strategic goals: increasing the Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) modal share by a minimum of 20%, improving reliability by 80%, and assuring 50% IWT capacity even during extreme weather events. These foreseen results have been defined with respect to the EC definition of “**Result**”, that is:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”¹³. Results may include “intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights, industrial designs, patents, plant variety rights) and similar forms of protection (e.g., rights for databases), as well as unprotected know-how (e.g., confidential material)”.

CRISTAL exploitation strategy was built primarily around the key concept of project’s exploitable results (KERs). The exploitable results are any tangible outputs of the project, including software, hardware, methodologies, services, models, etc., which are subject to further exploitation after the project through further R&D, dissemination, commercialisation, etc.

Out of the overall exploitable results, the CRISTAL exploitation strategy has prioritised the key exploitable results (KERs) i.e., those with a “*high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education*”¹⁴. To select and prioritise results, the EC recommends to projects to use the following criteria:

- 1) degree of innovation;
- 2) exploitability;
- 3) potential impact.

The conversion of initial Key Results and general project outcomes into **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** involved identifying specific, high-potential outputs and developing a strategic plan for their future application and impact, as detailed in Sub-section 5.1. This process is aimed to transform research knowledge into tangible commercial, societal, or policy benefits.

The conversion process of KRs and general outcomes into KERs was iterative and involved several key phases, which have been addressed throughout the project's lifecycle:

- **Identification:** Regularly assess all project outputs, such as data, new knowledge, software prototypes, methodologies, or policy recommendations. Prioritise those with the highest potential for downstream use or benefit.

¹³ EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

¹⁴ European Commission (2022), in Horizon Results Platform https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/HEU_Results_platform.pdf

- **Ownership and IPR Definition:** Clearly define who owns the results (Intellectual Property Rights - IPR). This is crucial for determining how results can be legally protected and used.
- **Target User and Market Analysis:** Identify the specific target users, stakeholders, and end-users who will benefit from the result. Conduct a market analysis to understand where the KER fits and what needs it solves, which helps in defining its value proposition.
- **Value Proposition Definition:** Articulate how the KER creates value for the identified users and how it is better than existing solutions.
- **Exploitation Strategy and Planning:** Develop a clear plan for how the KER will be utilised after the project ends. This includes:
 - ✓ **Commercialisation:** Creating new products, services, or spin-offs, or licensing the IP to third parties.
 - ✓ **Societal/Policy Impact:** Using results for standardisation activities, educational training, or to shape public policy.

The outcome of this conversion process is summarised in Table 13. In addition to details concerning the KERs, the status of the other KR is also briefly summarised - the KR that won't be pursued as KERs for further exploitation have been fully achieved during the project lifetime, except for KR13, which was just partially achieved.

Table 13: From Key Results (KRs) to Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Legend (Result Type, according to abbreviations used in the EC portal): PROD - Product (new or improved); SERV - Service (new or improved); BUS - Business model (new or improved); PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; LEARN - learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

<i>Key Results (KRs) (targeted by the project, as per the GA)</i>		<i>Key Exploitable Results (KERs) (achieved by CRISTAL, to be further pursued for exploitation)</i>				
KR no.	Result / innovation	KER no.	Result / Innovation	Description	Result owner	Result type
KR1	Roadmaps for needed developments and related administrative and regulatory framework, including the development of business and governance models, to achieve the targeted 20% market share growth – identification of information and infrastructure needs as well as data exchange and operational management requirements.	KER1	Roadmap based on the developed business and governance models (see KER3), including lessons learnt from their application to three case studies (the pilots) through the Living Labs.	CRISTAL roadmaps for the uptake of technologies to improve the resilience of inland waterway transport have been designed by defining the required technological, infrastructural, administrative, and regulatory measures to support a targeted 20% market share growth. These roadmaps integrate tailored business and governance models with clear requirements for data availability, information exchange, and operational corridor management, enabling scalable and institutionally anchored deployment across diverse European contexts.	SOGESCA UANT	PO BUS LEARN
KR2	A synchro/multi-modal corridor management system available for use to all involved actors (public authorities, logistics/mobility operators, passengers) and especially those parties responsible for crisis management and civil protection, for ensuring on-time shipments (and continuity of passenger transport) via IWT even in calamities situations in a minimum of 80% of cases.	KER2	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Toolbox for synchro-modal resource planning and operative operations preparation - an online platform designed to function as a single point of information for all stakeholders. It consolidates data from the DTs (see KER5) and external sources (like EuRIS) to provide early warnings, identify the impact of disruptions, and suggest Synchro-modal re-routing options involving road and rail.	CERTH	PROD SERV
KR3	Governance, business models and finance structures, technological developments and organisational models to ensure sustainable improvements for a successful implementation of the Good Navigation Status.	KER3	Governance, business models and finance structures developed for each innovative solution, along with organisational models necessary for a successful further implementation.	Business models have been defined for all CRISTAL innovations, then the governance models have been applied in Living Labs pertaining to each of the 3 Pilots. This enabled refinement of BMs and of governance models.	SOGESCA UANT	PO BUS LEARN

Key Results (KRs) (targeted by the project, as per the GA)		Key Exploitable Results (KERs) (achieved by CRISTAL, to be further pursued for exploitation)				
KR no.	Result / innovation	KER no.	Result / Innovation	Description	Result owner	Result type
KR4	Real-time monitoring system of water levels, hydrological conditions, infrastructure maintenance and resilience level, including a River Information Services (RIS)-Layer in which the collected data will be made available to the barge and surveillance operators.	KER4	Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)	The Acoustic Emission (AE) system detects transient elastic waves generated by phenomena such as micro-cracking, frictional activity, and other structural responses, which may indicate existence or development of defects within lock gates. AE provides early-warning indicators and localisation of active damage sources, enabling condition-based maintenance and reduction of unplanned outages.	CERTH	PROD SERV
		KER5	Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)	The radar-based non-destructive sub-surface inspection system (SIR) was designed for examination and inspection of IWW infrastructure assets, e.g., the sheer vertical concrete walls integral to lock infrastructure. The use of this advanced technology to assess the integrity of the inspected assets and provide information on their condition would enable preventive and/or predictive maintenance.	EUMO	PROD SERV
		KER6	Smart Buoys (SB)	The Smart Buoy (SB) system was developed as an integrated environmental monitoring and navigation support platform designed for IWW, combining floating sensor nodes, bridge-mounted devices, vessel transponders, and a central server application into a unified architecture for real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis.	L-PIT	PROD SERV

Key Results (KRs) (targeted by the project, as per the GA)		Key Exploitable Results (KERs) (achieved by CRISTAL, to be further pursued for exploitation)				
KR no.	Result / innovation	KER no.	Result / Innovation	Description	Result owner	Result type
		KER7	Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)	The FOS consists of a system equipped with Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors embedded into a submerged weighing platform, which uses a completely passive optical operating principle, eliminating the need for electrical power at the measurement point. The weighing platform is intended to indirectly estimate the height of the sediments heap through the direct measurement of its weight.	ENEA	PROD SERV
KR5	A digital twin incorporating real-time data (key result 4) and weather data for an infrastructure early warning and infrastructure maintenance system, as well as to support corridor management.	KER8	Digital Twins (DTs)	The DTs are virtual representations of physical assets (like locks or river segments) that aggregate data from various sensors (FOS, AE, SIR, SB) to provide forecasts, alerts, and visualisations, which would support decision-making for both transport operators and infrastructure managers.	FRAUNHOFER IML	PROD SERV
KR6	Exploitation of existing platform networks (e.g., https://fenix-network.eu/) to facilitate the interoperability among systems and the secured data and information exchange for supporting synchro/multimodality along a corridor.	N/A	N/A	KR to be pursued through KER3 (details above).	CERTH	PROD SERV
KR7	Applications to measure, in real time, the actual water levels and the IWT infrastructure maintenance and resilience by using novel subsurface inspection data to plan predictive maintenance and improving their resilience implemented, tested and validated in the three pilot regions.	N/A	N/A	KR achieved, the relevant sensor-based technologies have been developed, tested and validated (at different TRLs) in the project pilots. The outcomes are KERs 4a, 4b, 4c and 4d	CERTH EUMO L-PIT ENEA	PROD SERV
KR8	Completed implementation, testing and validation of the corridor management system, governance and technology innovations in the three pilot areas.	N/A	N/A	KR achieved, all technologies and technical innovations, along with governance and business models have been implemented and evaluated within the Validation Framework.	CERTH	SERV

<i>Key Results (KRs) (targeted by the project, as per the GA)</i>		<i>Key Exploitable Results (KERs) (achieved by CRISTAL, to be further pursued for exploitation)</i>				
KR no.	Result / innovation	KER no.	Result / Innovation	Description	Result owner	Result type
KR9	Completed implementation, testing and validation of the digital twins of the three pilot regions: Poland, Italy and France.	N/A	N/A	KR achieved, DTs have been implemented, tested and validated in the three pilot regions: Poland, Italy and France.	FRAUNHOFER IML	SERV
KR10	Roadmap for the improvement of IWT towards realisation of (EC IWT Transaction Plan 2021-2027 and EC Digital Inland Waterway Area2) flagship developments on a strategic level (European level).	KER9	Roadmap based on generic IWT use case, for the improvement of IWT towards realisation of flagship developments on a strategic level (European level).	KR achieved, roadmaps developed based on the "Deployment Roadmap" prepared in WP9 (Polish Pilot) and the governance analysis from WP7 (Italian Pilot). It outlines a strategic pathway (5 main recommendations) for policymakers, infrastructure managers, and industry stakeholders for the 2025–2035 Horizon.	UnGda	PO BUS LEARN
KR11	Roadmap for individual pilot regions towards realisation of flagship developments (pilot level).	N/A	N/A	KR achieved, roadmaps developed based on lessons learnt in the three pilot regions: Poland, Italy and France.	UniCa VNF L-PIT	PO BUS
KR12	Roadmap for individual stakeholders (engineers, environmentalists, assets and risks managers, logistic & fleet professionals and trainers, procurement managers, organisation managers, transport/logistic and land planning managers, policy makers) towards realisation of flagship developments (individual organisation level).	N/A	N/A	KR achieved, roadmaps developed based on lessons learnt from the application of the living lab governance model to the three case studies.	SOGESCA UANT	PO BUS
KR13	Roadmap for financial sector towards realisation of flagship developments (individual organisation level), in line with the EC Taxonomy, taking into account the results of the "Maritime taxonomy".	N/A	N/A	KR partially achieved due to difficulties to involve and work with financial sector in the three pilot regions, which is a pre-requisite for the KR.	UniCa VNF L-PIT	PO BUS

5.3. Exploitation plans (breakdown per each partner)

Lukasiewicz - Poznanski Instytut Technologiczny (L-PIT)

Foreground IP:

L-PIT achieved foreground is twofold:

1. The implementation of the EPCIS open standard (developed by the GS1 organisation) as software (event-based database) was conducted by L-PIT with the cooperation of the GS1 organisation, therefore, the distribution of rights to the implementation have been established as an equal (50/50%) share. The database constitutes know-how and together with GS1, L-PIT undertake to keep the subject matter of the contract confidential. The software code itself is a copyrighted work. However, this software, as a significant L-PIT background, enabled the use and exploitation of EPCIS in tests, pilot mode and for validations within CRISTAL. The standard information exchange model for EPCIS was used, and the project developed an extension to the Object Event module representing the recording of events occurring with one or more physical or digital objects. The registration of objects was trialled in a standard EPCIS data exchange format which was not copyrighted.
2. The Smart Buoys (SB) technology was developed based on relevant background (know-how on integration of different internal communication protocols between buoy components using a single board computer). The foreground achieved includes protocols at the level of analysis of analogue signals sent by integrated devices. The product, in functional terms (as technology integrating various communication protocols) can be protected in the event of commoditisation.

Exploitation Plan:

SERV - Service (new or improved); PROD - Product (new or improved)

EPCIS was developed as a back-up communication channel during the CRISTAL project for the transmission of messages from river buoys. If the river buoys are commercialised, it will be possible to further develop EPCIS for this scope, and use the system to further collect and transmit customer data on the EPCIS platform.

L-PIT will pursue the exploitation of **SB technology - KER6** - as its owner. The product is envisaged for commercialisation for users operating on rivers where RIS is not operational, on non-major smaller rivers and canals. The communication and functional module of the solution will allow users to increase the navigability of the routes.

The product in functional terms can be protected in the event of commoditisation. The work product of the L-PIT (technology integrating various communication protocols) in this case will be a company secret.

L-PIT will also exploit the Smart Buoy (SB) system as an integrated environmental monitoring and navigation support platform designed for IWW, combining floating sensor nodes, bridge-mounted devices, vessel transponders, and a central server application into a unified architecture for real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis.

Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE)

Foreground IP:

ALICE Foreground includes:

- Co-created policy, governance and business model insights for climate-resilient and synchromodal inland waterway logistics.
- Stakeholder-driven roadmaps and recommendations supporting the integration of IWT into multimodal and supply chain operations.
- Contributions to exploitation, dissemination and uptake strategies, ensuring alignment with EU logistics priorities.

- Consolidated lessons learned and best practices from pilots and multi-stakeholder workshops, feeding EU policy and standardisation discussions.

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy.

- Integrating CRISTAL foreground knowledge into ALICE strategic research and innovation agendas (SRIA) and thematic roadmaps. Using project outcomes to support policy recommendations towards the European Commission and EU Member States on resilient, low-emission logistics and Inland Waterway Transport.
- Allowing wide dissemination and uptake through ALICE's European network of industry, logistics operators, ports, and technology providers.
- Supporting replication and scaling of CRISTAL governance models, synchro-modal concepts and best practices across European logistics corridors.
- Feeding results into future Horizon Europe and innovation initiatives and cross-ETP collaboration activities

Agenzia Nazionale Per Le Nuove Tecnologie, L'energia E Lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile (ENEA)

Foreground IP:

Development and testing of Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) technology, from initial TRL2 (background - existing patent 102022000007103 (Italy) on Procedure for the Implementation of a Fiber Optic Sensor Chain and Fiber Optic Sensor Chain) to TRL4-5 (validated in simulated environment). The FOS system was designed to enable uninterrupted, real-time detection of sediment accumulation buildup in free-flowing waterways, thereby supporting informed decision-making on the navigability of high-risk sections.

Exploitation Plan:

PROD - Product (new or improved)

ENEA will pursue the exploitation of **FOS technology – KER7** - as its owner. The exploitation strategy aims to patent, commercialise, and deploy the FOS technology. CRISTAL results will be exploited by advancing the patented fibre optic sensor technology toward commercialisation, large-scale deployment, and integration into waterway management systems. This will enable continuous, real-time monitoring of sediment and obstruction buildup in free-flowing waterways, provide actionable intelligence on the navigability of critical sections, and support authorities and infrastructure managers in predictive maintenance, risk mitigation, and safer navigation operations

Agenzia Interregionale Per Il Fiume Po (AIPo)

Foreground IP:

AIPo foreground includes:

- Knowledge on the navigability conditions prediction model and Smart Bulletin, which have been tested in the Italian pilot. The statistical model for navigability prediction can be shared on request with other public navigation managers.
- Knowledge of the Italian IWW scenarios.
- Relationships established with several Italian IWW stakeholders.
- Knowledge of the Living Lab methodology, and associated methods and tools used in LLs.

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; SERV - Service (new or improved)

The navigability conditions of the River Po will be made available to all stakeholders through the "Smart Bulletin". This can be accessed from both the AIPo website and the "Il Portolano del Po" App. Also, through dissemination

throughout stakeholders, AIPO will provide support towards further exploitation of roadmaps – **KER1**, and business and governance models - **KER3**.

Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung der Angewandten Forschung (FRAUNHOFER)

Foreground IP:

Digital Twins (DTs) have been developed in the project based on background on data sources and the APIs for accessing pre-existing historic sources, as well as knowledge of software architecture and software development.

The source code of DT for the Water Level is not shared and is commercially secret. The DT Locks / DT Buoy: from the DT perspective, the sensor data is handled and processed here, so if certain restrictions apply there (e.g., for the AE system) they should also apply to the DT. The technology providers are key to the future development. In relation to DTs, these are developed software that does not have to/cannot be patented in the first approach but remain commercially secret. Foreground related to DT Locks and DT Buoy includes more or less the entire development of the DTs, which were created from scratch based on the requirements and scenarios with the various technologies.

Exploitation Plan:

PROD - Product (new or improved); SERV - Service (new or improved)

FRAUNHOFET ILM will pursue the exploitation of **Digital Twins – KER8** - as its owner. Results from the CRISTAL project will be used for further research and to extend the functionalities for other use cases. Additionally, the DTs will be developed for use for other waterways.

Infrastrutture Venete (IV)

Foreground IP:

IV foreground includes:

- Knowledge on the cold ironing technology (from feasibility study within the Italian pilot, including: report for cold ironing facilities along relevant IWWs managed by IV (copyright); detailed design documents for typical plants at 4 landing points (trade secret).
- Knowledge of the Italian IWW scenarios.
- Knowledge of the Living Lab methodology, and associated methods and tools used in LLs.

Exploitation Plan:

INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; SERV - Service (new or improved)

The detailed evaluation carried out in the Italian pilot CRISTAL facilitate the start-up activities that are considered necessary to complete the preparatory steps paving the way to the creation of a dedicated cold-ironing facility.

The overall knowledge acquired through the studies carried out within the framework of the CRISTAL project will be used to define some key future steps of development of specific types of infrastructures among the IWW managed by IV. The evaluation template has effectively assessed the feasibility of future interventions along the IWW managed by Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l. thus allowing prioritisation of future financing decisions. Therefore, IV will collaborate with SOGESCA for further exploitation of **Roadmaps (KER1)**.

Also, potential further dissemination of the CRISTAL outcomes is foreseen.

Sogesca (SOGESCA)

Foreground IP:

Good knowledge of the Living Lab methodology, as main contributors to LLs developed for CRISTAL. Good awareness of the stakeholder engagement process, including and involving: engineers, environmentalists, assets and risks managers, logistic & fleet professionals and trainers, procurement managers, organisation managers, transport/logistic and land planning managers, policy makers. Stakeholders' assessment on management systems, business continuity, climate-change problems related, mitigation and adaptation actions, ESG reports, involvement of public authorities.

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved)

SOGESCA will pursue the exploitation of **Roadmaps (KER1)** and **Business and governance models (KER3)**, which they co-own along with UAntwerpen. Amongst the first steps, already made, the roadmaps developed based on the CRISTAL information have been presented to the Italian Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport and shared with the entire community of stakeholders in the Padano-Veneto waterway system. Together with the Manifesto for Sustainable Development, it can serve as a guideline for ensuring future improvement of the entire system to provide policy recommendations and for the development of new business models based on roadmaps for European IWWs.

Universiteit Antwerpen (UAntwerpen)

Foreground IP:

The University of Antwerpen (UAntwerpen) has achieved significant knowledge regarding transport economics, in general, and IWT, in particular. This knowledge complements similar existing knowledge obtained via other R&D projects and funded research projects.

Exploitation Plan: LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved); LEARN - learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

UAntwerpen will pursue the exploitation of **Roadmaps (KER1)** and **Business and governance models (KER3)**, which they co-own along with SOGESCA. In addition, the integration of CRISTAL knowledge into academia postgraduate teaching is foreseen, along with use for further dissemination through papers in peer-reviewed journals. Also, the knowledge achieved in CRISTAL will support raising the organisation's profile, which may benefit for future research and consultancy projects.

Uniwersytet Gdanski (UnGda)

Foreground IP:

Based on general background comprising business models for implementing IWW into supply chains, in environments excluding inland navigation due to unsatisfied capacity/performance, UnGda has achieved verified business models, with special focus on project cargo and dry bulk cargo in direct services to/from seaport. There is potential for the IPR related to these validated models to be protected in the future. In addition, knowledge achieved includes: business models insights for climate-resilient, synchromodal inland waterway logistics recommendation and policy, and new socio-economic knowledge on IWT perception in Poland.

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved); LEARN - learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

UnGda will pursue the exploitation of the **Roadmap based on generic IWT use case (KER9)**, as its owner. In addition, the achieved knowledge will be used for further development and academic purposes, including plans for continuous research on IWT development.

Voies Navigables de France (VNF)

Foreground IP:

VNF background, comprising detailed information concerning the state of VNF infrastructure (information that is commercially sensitive and confidential) was essential for different activities in the project. Based on this background and activities in CRISTAL, VNF achieved relevant knowledge on the living lab approach, evidencing CRISTAL technologies benefit recognising their potential value in improving day-to-day maintenance and traffic management practices. Also, the stakeholder-driven roadmaps and recommendations supporting the integration of IWT into multimodal and supply chain operations is a valuable foreground that may be further exploited.

Exploitation Plan:

SERV - Service (new or improved); BUS - Business model (new or improved)

The smart buoys (part of “own initiatives” of the French pilot) may be further investigated in other projects and then, depending on results, such system may be developed as an integrated environmental monitoring and navigation support platform designed for French IWW, combining floating sensor nodes, bridge-mounted devices, vessel transponders, and a central server application into a unified architecture for real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis (relating and in support to **KER6**).

Fluv'IOTe could be further investigated with national authorities.

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology will be further investigated and tested internally as a maintenance tool based on the equipment provided by EUMO to VNF for data collection (relating and in support to **KER5**).

The living lab approach could be further implemented into other projects and support early adoption by pilot-related authorities, building on the Living Lab experience, particularly for infrastructure managers and corridor operators (relating and in support to **KER1**).

KTI Kozlekedestudományi Intézet (KTI)

Foreground IP:

KTI achieved know-how and learnt lessons on strengthening inland waterway transport resilience (governance, stakeholder coordination, and uptake pathways), in particular from the contributions to the project exploitation, dissemination and communication strategy, ensuring alignment with EU inland navigation and multimodal logistics priorities and with national policy needs.

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved); LEARN - learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

KTI will continue the dissemination of results and encouraging IWT usage and uptake beyond project closure by: (i) mainstreaming CRISTAL results into Hungarian transport strategy development and policy advisory processes (relating to, and supporting **KER1**); (ii) embedding the knowledge in the academic knowledge base through publications, teaching materials and further research; (iii) sustaining the triple-helix cooperation by transferring practical insights to industry and public authorities via follow-up workshops, targeted stakeholder exchanges and guidance material (relating to, and supporting **KER9**); and (iv) leveraging the outcomes in follow-up EU and national R&I proposals/projects.

Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

Foreground IP:

CERTH foreground includes:

- All IPR regarding the SCMS and its functionalities. No patent has been filed by the end of the project, however, the synchro-modal route planning algorithm that was developed will remain confidential, as well as the algorithms for route planning and data standardisation. The Toolbox for synchro-modal resource planning and cooperative preparation of operations will be hosted on CERTH's servers and will be maintained and exploited by CERTH after the completion of the project as an open-source platform.
- Development, testing and validation of AE technology, including extensive knowledge in the application and interpretation of Acoustic Emission (AE) techniques.
- Consolidated lessons learned and best practices from pilots and multi-stakeholder workshops, which may feed into EU policy and standardisation discussions.

Exploitation Plan:

PROD - Product (new or improved); SERV - Service (new or improved); PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved)

CERTH will pursue the exploitation of **SCMS (KER2)** and **AE technology (KER4)** as their owner. The Toolbox for synchro-modal resource planning and operative operations preparation will be further exploited as an online platform designed to function as a single point of information for all stakeholders (achieved **KR2**). The use of the SCMS on pilot sites will be pursued beyond the project duration, including further development of the system through future EU-funded projects.

The exploitation of Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE) may be pursued as a service provided in predictive maintenance of large to very large infrastructures. Further use and development will be also considered in other EU projects for large infrastructures.

Also, CERTH will support SOGESCA and UAntwerpen in further exploitation of governance, business models and finance structures developed for each innovative solution, along with organisational models necessary for a successful further implementation (relating and in support to **KER3**).

Unione Italiana Delle Camere di Commercio Industria Artigianato E Agricoltura, Unioncamere (UniCa)

and

Uniontrasporti (UniTra)

Foreground IP:

UniCa and UniTra achieved excellent knowledge of the Italian IWW scenario, and established very good relationships with key Italian IWW stakeholders. Also, they achieved relevant knowledge on the creation and application of roadmaps to support individual pilot regions towards realisation of flagship developments (pilot level).

Exploitation Plan:

PO - Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; BUS - Business model (new or improved)

UniCa and UniTra will collaborate between them and with Italian stakeholders to support and promote an increased use of inland waterways for both goods and passengers, as a reliable, efficient and eco-sustainable transport mode in alternative but also in synergies with road and rail transport.

Also, they will support SOGESCA and UAntwerpen in further exploitation of governance, business models and finance structures developed for each innovative solution, along with organisational models necessary for a successful further implementation (relating and in support to **KER3**).

Euromobilita (EUMO)

Foreground IP:

Existing relevant background achieved in previous research projects (e.g., knowledge of the operation of ground penetrating radar for rail infrastructure, particularly tunnels) allowed EUMO to achieve excellent knowledge of the practical application of radar in complex infrastructure and real-life working environment. Also, excellent skills in the design, development and fabrication of subsurface radar testing equipment.

The radar system developed in CRISTAL - Subsurface inspection Radar (SIR) is not patentable as a complete system, as it builds on existing innovative technologies. However, SIR can certainly be exploited for market opportunities, together with the algorithms developed and owned by UNEW.

Exploitation Plan:

PROD - Product (new or improved); SERV - Service (new or improved)

EUMO will pursue the exploitation of **SIR technology – KER5** - as its owner. There is an emerging commercial arrangement with VNF, which recognises the security/confidentiality issues with regard to VNF data (not just with regard to locks). This arrangement is based on VNF collecting the SIR data using the SIR equipment left by EUMO with VNF, for their validation of the data collection system on different locks.

The next step is for EUMO to move forward from the preproduction prototype demonstrated on the Seine and Moselle and use the lessons learnt to produce a robust commercial system that can be easily transported for use on lock structures and other IWW infrastructures (e.g., dams). Further exploitation of SIR on any surface may be viable commercially using first adopter advantage.

Newcastle University (UNEW)

Foreground IP:

UNEW foreground includes:

- In-depth knowledge on operating GPR equipment and subsequent processing of acquired data. Including use of specialised software, data processing methods, visualisation tools and algorithms.
- Knowledge on design and operation of complex systems for inspection of large infrastructure assets.
- Knowledge on maintenance practice for large IWW infrastructure assets. Including types of damages and their causes, maintenance operations, inspection methods, etc.
- Knowledge on management of complex big data (inc. media files resulting from processing of GPR scanning data). Including use of Digital Twin solution for the scope (interfaces, data transfer, communication protocols, etc.).
- In-depth knowledge on assessment and technical validation of sensor-based systems at different TRLs. Including KPIs and requirements, testing methods, test planning, etc.

Exploitation Plan:

PROD - Product (new or improved); SERV - Service (new or improved); BUS - Business model (new or improved); LEARN - learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

UNEW will support EUMO in pursuing exploitation of **SIR technology (KER5)**, as a new product or new service. UNEW could potentially claim patent royalties if EUMO would consider applying for a patent to protect the subsurface inspection system (SIR) as a whole (inc. design of modular platform, data collection and processing method, etc.), or just elements of SIR system and inspection methodology.

Also, UNEW will support SOGESCA and UAntwerpen in further exploitation of business models developed for each innovative solution (relating and in support to **KER3**).

In addition, as academic organisation, specific exploitation activities will include:

- Further publications to increase visibility and credibility of researchers involved in CRISTAL.
- Use of achieved knowledge in postgraduate teaching, and formal integration in future curriculae.
- Use of knowledge and skills for further similar work in potential research projects in transport area or civil engineering.

5.4. Risks for Exploitation & Mitigation Measures

Risks to successful exploitation have been consistently identified and considered by the CRISTAL IPEB, being discussed and analysed in order to determine the most effective mitigation measures. In principle, the risks are typically categorised into technical, legal, and market-related factors. The most relevant risks for exploitation identified and addressed by the CRISTAL IPEB are:

- **Intellectual Property (IP) Issue:** Failure to clearly define "background" (pre-existing knowledge) versus "foreground" (results generated during the project) can lead to legal deadlocks. Practically, some results may end without a partner clearly claiming them, while others may be disputed between several partners.
- **Market Viability Issues:** Results may lack news value or fail to meet real market needs, making them difficult to scale or commercialise.
- **Lack of Partner Commitment:** Exploitation often requires post-project investment; if partners have conflicting expectations or lack resources to continue, results may remain unused.
- **Regulatory & Ethical Barriers:** Potential gaps in current regulatory framework, which may require changes or updates of current legislation and/or norms, or failure to align with ethical standards (e.g., data protection, human subjects research) can become barriers to the transition from research to application.
- **Potential Undesirable Negative Impacts:** Implementation of research outcomes (hardware, software, models, etc.) might lead to unforeseen and undesirable negative impacts on users, general public, environment where the innovation is being implemented, etc.

In order to address these potential risks, the CRISTAL IPEB has considered different potential measures, and prioritised the following main **Mitigation Strategies**:

1. **Exploitation Plan IPR strategy:** Maintaining a living **IPEB log** that summarises the Exploitation and IPR strategy described in Sub-section 5.1, to regularly address all issues related to KERs (ownership, exploitation plans, target audiences, etc.).
2. **Consortium Agreement:** Use a formal agreement to clarify partner roles, expectations, and IPR management before the project starts.
3. **Use of EC Support Services:** Utilise tools such as the Horizon Results Platform to find third-party organisations that may be interested in further exploitation of CRISTAL KERs, if the owner partners cannot use the results.
4. **Regulation & Ethics Reviews:** Conduct assessments of current regulatory framework to identify any barriers that may prevent or delay the market uptake of CRISTAL results, and make efforts to initiate the necessary changes, if any such issues would be identified (i.e., contact regulatory and/or standardisation bodies, prepare propositions for changes and updates, etc.).

5.5. Roadmap for Exploitation of CRISTAL Project Results Beyond the Project Lifetime

Considering the potential for further exploitation of the project results, a roadmap for exploitation of CRISTAL results beyond the project lifetime was developed within Task 11.2 activities, with direct involvement of all IPEB members. The objective of this roadmap is to define a structured, phased approach for the exploitation of the project results beyond the project lifetime, ensuring their sustained impact in the transport sector - particularly inland waterway transport (IWT) - while enabling uptake in related domains such as multimodal logistics, infrastructure management, environmental monitoring, and public policy.

The roadmap addresses technical, organisational, market, and policy dimensions and builds upon the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) achieved during the project. It targets both short-term post-project continuation activities and long-term deployment pathways at regional, national, and European levels.

5.5.1. Policy and Call Alignment

The exploitation roadmap of the CRISTAL project is fully aligned with the objectives of **Horizon Europe Cluster 5**, in particular with destinations addressing **sustainable, resilient, and digital mobility systems**, climate adaptation, and infrastructure resilience. The roadmap supports key EU strategies and policy frameworks, including the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy¹⁵, NAIADES III¹⁶, the Digital Inland Waterway Area¹⁷, the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy¹⁸, and the TEN-T Regulation¹⁹.

CRISTAL results contribute directly to Cluster 5 priorities by enabling:

- Modal shift towards low-carbon inland waterway transport (IWT);
- Increased resilience of transport infrastructure to climate extremes;
- Digitalisation and interoperability across transport modes;
- Evidence-based policymaking and governance innovation.

5.5.2. Exploitation Vision and Objectives

The long-term exploitation vision is to establish **inland waterways as a reliable, climate-resilient, and digitally integrated transport mode**, fully embedded within multimodal European transport corridors.

The specific exploitation objectives are to:

- Bring mature CRISTAL Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to operational and commercial deployment;
- Support uptake by infrastructure managers, corridor authorities, and transport operators;
- Enable policy and regulatory implementation through validated roadmaps and governance models;

¹⁵ Communication COM/2020/789 from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy – putting European transport on track for the future. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0789>

¹⁶ Communication COM/2021/324 from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - NAIADES III: Boosting future-proof European inland waterway transport. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0324>

¹⁷ Proposal COM/2024/33 for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services (RIS) on inland waterways in the Community. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52024PC0033>

¹⁸ Communication COM/2021/82 from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:82:FIN>

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on Union guidelines for the development of the trans-European transport network. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1679>

- Facilitate transfer of CRISTAL solutions to other transport and infrastructure domains.

Phased Exploitation Roadmap

Phase 1: Post-Project Consolidation and Early Uptake (0–2 Years)

Objectives: Market readiness, policy transfer, and first deployments.

Key actions:

- **Consolidation and protection of CRISTAL KERs**, including IPR safeguarding and licensing strategies, in line with the Consortium Agreement.
- **Technical maturation and integration** of operational tools, notably:
 - ✓ **KER2** (Synchro-modal Corridor Management System) for disruption management and rerouting;
 - ✓ **KER4–KER7** (AE, SIR, SB, FOS sensor systems) for infrastructure and environmental monitoring;
 - ✓ **KER8** (Digital Twins) as an integrative decision-support layer.
- **Early adoption by pilot-related authorities**, building on Living Lab experience, particularly for infrastructure managers and corridor operators.
- **Exploitation of CRISTAL roadmaps and governance models:**
 - ✓ **KER1** and **KER3** for business and governance implementation at organisational and corridor levels;
 - ✓ **KER9** for policy-level alignment with EU flagship initiatives.
- **Targeted dissemination to policymakers**, through policy briefs and stakeholder workshops addressing resilience, climate adaptation, and digitalisation.

Expected outcomes:

- Initial service contracts or public procurement uptake;
- Inclusion of CRISTAL recommendations in regional or national transport strategies;
- Increased TRL progression for selected KERs.

Phase 2: Scaling, Replication and Cross-Modal Integration (2–5 Years)

Objectives: Deployment at scale and integration into multimodal systems.

Key actions:

- **Scaling up KER2 and KER8** across additional inland waterway corridors and river basins, ensuring interoperability with rail and road platforms.
- **Operational deployment of monitoring solutions** (KER4–KER7) within asset management and maintenance planning of waterway authorities, contributing to predictive and preventive maintenance strategies.
- **Standardisation and harmonisation activities**, leveraging CRISTAL results to inform RIS evolution, data-sharing frameworks, and digital twin best practices.
- **Replication beyond IWT**, applying CRISTAL technologies and methodologies to:
 - ✓ ports and coastal infrastructure,
 - ✓ bridges, tunnels, and other critical transport assets,
 - ✓ flood-risk and climate adaptation infrastructure.
- **Capacity building and training**, using CRISTAL methodologies, governance models (KER3), and roadmaps (KER1, KER9) for professional education and organisational transformation.

Expected outcomes:

- Wider market uptake and stable exploitation pathways;
- Recognition of CRISTAL solutions as reference implementations;
- Contribution to EU-wide resilience and digital transport objectives.

Phase 3: Long-Term Systemic Impact and Policy Embedding (5+ Years)

Objectives: Structural change and long-term sustainability.

Key actions:

- **Embedding CRISTAL results into long-term infrastructure and investment planning**, including alignment with EU Taxonomy and sustainable finance frameworks.
- **Policy uptake of CRISTAL roadmaps**, particularly **KER9**, to support EU and national decision-making on IWT modernisation and climate resilience.
- **Establishment of innovation ecosystems**, fostering cooperation between public authorities, industry, research organisations, and financial stakeholders.
- **Continuous innovation and follow-up R&I**, building on CRISTAL Digital Twins (KER8) and sensor technologies (KER4–KER7) for AI-enabled forecasting and decision support.

Expected outcomes:

- Long-term improvements in reliability and resilience of inland waterways;
- Sustained modal shift and emissions reduction;
- Enduring contribution to European transport competitiveness.

5.5.3. Target Stakeholders and Markets

The exploitation roadmap addresses:

- Inland waterway and transport infrastructure authorities;
- Multimodal corridor managers and logistics operators;
- Public administrations and policymakers at EU and national levels;
- Engineering and infrastructure management sectors;
- Research, education, and training organisations.

5.5.4. Risk Management and Enablers

Key risks include market fragmentation, regulatory delays, and investment constraints. Mitigation measures rely on:

- Clear IPR and governance arrangements;
- Early engagement with authorities and standardisation bodies;
- Use of EU exploitation support services and partnerships.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

Task 11.2 of the CRISTAL project has achieved its objectives, and the outcomes are presented in the previous sections of this report, structured along three distinct but connected topics:

1. European IWT market and policy.
2. Business models and economic impacts
3. Exploitation strategy and plans.

The conclusions are explicitly derived from the content of the report; however, they do not restate the document, but interpret, consolidate, and extrapolate its findings.

Furthermore, based on the drawn conclusions, recommendations are proposed to support the effective uptake, scaling, and long-term sustainability of CRISTAL results and similar initiatives in the European Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) sector. These recommendations address **policy makers, infrastructure managers, market actors, and technology providers**, and focus on creating the enabling conditions required to translate innovation into measurable impact.

6.1. European IWT Market and Policy

6.1.1. Conclusions

The CRISTAL project confirms that the European IWT market is characterised by a **structural underutilisation paradox**: despite clear environmental, energy-efficiency, and capacity advantages, IWT remains marginal in logistics decision-making. The market analysis shows that this is not due to a lack of physical infrastructure alone, but rather to systemic weaknesses in reliability, predictability, digital integration, and governance coordination.

A key conclusion is that **market demand for IWT does not fail at the level of transport capacity, but at the level of confidence**. Shippers, logistics service providers, and multimodal planners systematically prioritise modes that offer predictable service, real-time visibility, and clear risk management mechanisms. IWT, as currently organised, struggles to meet these expectations, even in corridors where waterways are physically available. CRISTAL's market analysis and stakeholder workshops consistently confirmed that **unpredictability, rather than cost, is now the dominant barrier** to wider IWT uptake.

The market segmentation carried out within CRISTAL demonstrates that IWT is not a single market but a **multi-layered ecosystem** involving infrastructure managers, authorities, operators, logistics actors, ports, technology providers, and policy makers. The presence of more than 170 identified stakeholders across pilots illustrates that **value creation in IWT depends on coordinated action across multiple actors**, and that isolated technological solutions are unlikely to achieve market penetration on their own. This explains why previous innovation efforts often remained confined to pilots.

From a market trend perspective, CRISTAL confirms a **moderately positive growth outlook** for inland waterway freight transport, driven by sustainability policies, congestion on roads, and increasing pressure to decarbonise logistics chains. However, the analysis also highlights that growth will not be automatic. Climate-induced hydrological variability, aging infrastructure, and fragmented governance increasingly threaten service reliability. These pressures transform digitalisation from a “nice-to-have” into a **market-enabling condition**.

The strongest market opportunity identified is the shift from asset-centric to **corridor-level, data-driven transport management**. Stakeholders clearly recognise the value of real-time monitoring, forecasting, and shared situational awareness, particularly when delivered through interoperable platforms rather than proprietary silos. The alignment of CRISTAL with the DINA framework and ALICE recommendations positions its results within an emerging European market logic that favours **shared digital infrastructures over isolated tools**.

In conclusion, CRISTAL shows that the IWT market will not expand through incremental efficiency gains alone. Market growth depends on restoring trust in IWT as a **reliable, predictable, and digitally integrated mode**, capable of functioning as a credible component of modern multimodal supply chains. CRISTAL's technologies and governance models directly address this market gap.

6.1.2. Recommendations

Reposition Inland Waterways as a Reliable System, Not a Static Asset

A central recommendation is to shift the policy and market narrative around IWT from infrastructure availability to **system reliability and predictability**. Policy frameworks, funding instruments, and performance indicators should explicitly prioritise reliability, resilience, and service continuity, rather than only capacity expansion or modal share metrics.

EU and national policies should:

- Integrate reliability and resilience indicators into IWT performance monitoring.
- Explicitly recognise digital monitoring, forecasting, and decision-support systems as **core transport infrastructure**, not ancillary tools.
- Avoid treating IWT as a residual mode, and instead promote it as a **managed, data-driven transport system** comparable to rail and road.

This repositioning is essential to rebuild confidence among shippers and logistics planners and to support modal shift objectives.

Align IWT Digitalisation with European Frameworks (DINA, RIS, TEN-T)

CRISTAL confirms the importance of corridor-level, interoperable digital infrastructures. Therefore, future EU programmes should:

- Mandate alignment of IWT digital solutions with the **DINA framework** and existing RIS standards.
- Promote interoperability, open interfaces, and data sharing as eligibility conditions for public funding.
- Support cross-border digital continuity on TEN-T inland corridors, avoiding fragmented national implementations.

This approach will reduce duplication, enhance scalability, and enable market actors to integrate IWT more easily into multimodal logistics chains.

6.2. Business and Economic Impact

6.2.1. Conclusions

The business and economic assessment carried out in CRISTAL leads to a clear and differentiated conclusion: **economic value is real, but unevenly distributed across technologies and strongly dependent on context, governance, and scale.**

At a systemic level, the project demonstrates that the **primary economic benefits of CRISTAL do not arise from direct productivity gains**, but from avoided costs: reduced unplanned disruptions, fewer emergency repairs, improved maintenance planning, better use of infrastructure capacity, and lower risk exposure for operators and logistics actors. Reliability and resilience emerge as the dominant economic drivers, outweighing pure efficiency metrics such as speed or unit cost.

The analysis confirms that **sensor-based technologies targeting infrastructure condition** (Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar) show the clearest and most robust business cases. Their value propositions are well understood by infrastructure managers, their cost structures are relatively transparent, and their benefits are

directly linked to maintenance optimisation and risk reduction. Living Lab validation confirms strong acceptance of these technologies when they are positioned as **long-term monitoring and expert service solutions**, rather than standalone hardware products. From an economic perspective, these solutions support a shift from reactive to predictive maintenance, extending asset lifetimes and smoothing investment cycles.

In contrast, technologies addressing **hydrological variability and navigability conditions** (Smart Buoys and Fibre Optic Sensors) show more conditional or long-term economic viability. Smart Buoys generate clear operational value through real-time data provision, but their economic performance is highly sensitive to baseline navigability and climate conditions. Fibre Optic Sensors demonstrate strong strategic relevance for climate resilience and dredging optimisation, but their current cost structure places them beyond immediate market viability. The conclusion is that such technologies are **economically justified primarily as public or co-funded infrastructure investments**, rather than through private market mechanisms.

Digital solutions (Digital Twins and SCMS) produce the **highest systemic economic value**, but also face the greatest challenges in monetisation. The project conclusively invalidates the idea of Digital Twins as standalone commercial products. Instead, they function as **value multipliers and integration layers**, enhancing the benefits of sensor data and enabling advanced decision support. Their economic justification lies in system-level gains rather than direct revenue generation.

The Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) emerges as the **strategic economic backbone** of the CRISTAL portfolio. Stakeholders strongly value its alerting, information consolidation, and planning support functions, and express willingness to pay for reliability-enhancing services. However, the business case is highly sensitive to traffic volumes, governance arrangements, and phased deployment. Full synchronodal re-routing remains premature, confirming that economic value should be realised incrementally, starting with information and alert services.

Across pilots, the economic assessment shows that **hybrid business models combining public funding and market revenues are not a weakness but a necessity**. Many benefits of CRISTAL technologies exhibit public-good characteristics (safety, emissions reduction, network resilience), which cannot be fully captured by private actors. The Living Labs confirmed that stakeholders accept this logic, provided responsibilities, data governance, and long-term ownership are clearly defined.

In summary, CRISTAL demonstrates that economic viability in IWT innovation depends less on technological sophistication and more on **institutional embedding, scale, and integration**. When these conditions are met, the economic benefits outweigh costs, particularly through avoided disruptions and improved resilience.

6.2.2. Recommendations

Promote Hybrid Public–Private Business Models as the Norm

The economic assessment demonstrates that many benefits of IWT digitalisation and infrastructure monitoring are **systemic and public in nature** (e.g., resilience, safety, emissions reduction). As a result, purely commercial business models are often insufficient, hence, the main recommendations are:

- Encourage **hybrid business models** combining public funding, service contracts, and market revenues.
- Design funding schemes that support long-term operational costs (data platforms, monitoring services), not only capital investments.
- Accept public co-funding as a legitimate and necessary component of economically viable IWT innovation.

These recommendations should be reflected in EU calls, national funding programmes, and procurement strategies.

Prioritise Service-Oriented Exploitation over Product Sales

CRISTAL shows that infrastructure managers and authorities value **interpreted, decision-ready services**, rather than raw data or standalone hardware. Therefore:

- Sensor-based technologies should be commercialised primarily through **monitoring and inspection services**, not equipment sales.
- Business models should include expert interpretation, integration with Digital Twins, and long-term partnerships.
- Public procurement should be adapted to facilitate outcome-based and service-based contracts.

This shift reduces adoption barriers and aligns business models with actual operational needs.

Differentiate Investment Strategies by Technology Maturity and Role

A “one-size-fits-all” investment logic is not appropriate. Instead:

- Near-market technologies (e.g., AE, SIR) should be supported through deployment-oriented funding and framework contracts.
- Enabling technologies (Digital Twins, SCMS) should be funded as shared digital infrastructure with long-term operational mandates.
- High-cost, long-term innovations (e.g., Fibre Optic Sensors) should be embedded in **strategic public investment and research programmes**, especially those addressing climate adaptation.

This differentiation improves resource allocation and avoids unrealistic commercial expectations.

6.3. Exploitation Strategy and Plans

6.3.1. Conclusions

The exploitation analysis leads to a central conclusion: **successful exploitation of CRISTAL results requires differentiated, phased, and governance-led strategies rather than a single commercialisation pathway.**

First, CRISTAL confirms that exploitation potential varies significantly across results. Sensor-based infrastructure monitoring solutions (AE and SIR) are closest to market readiness and can be exploited through **service-oriented business models**, targeting infrastructure managers via long-term contracts and framework agreements. Their exploitation should prioritise standardisation, integration with Digital Twins, and accumulation of long-term datasets, which increase value over time.

Smart Buoys and Fibre Optic Sensors require more selective exploitation strategies. Smart Buoys are suitable for **targeted deployment in stable or strategically important corridors**, often linked to national or regional programmes. Fibre Optic Sensors, by contrast, should be positioned within **long-term public investment and research-driven programmes**, focusing on climate adaptation and strategic infrastructure planning rather than near-term commercial return.

Digital Twins and the SCMS should be exploited as **enabling digital infrastructure components**, not as isolated products. Their exploitation logic is ecosystem-based: licensing, integration, and bundling within broader corridor-level digital platforms. The SCMS, in particular, provides a unifying exploitation vehicle capable of aggregating CRISTAL results and interfacing with existing European systems (RIS, EuRIS, DINA-aligned platforms). Phased deployment, starting with alerting and information services, is essential to build trust and demonstrate value before expanding functionality.

A critical conclusion concerns **governance and ownership**. The project clearly demonstrates that exploitation will fail if responsibilities for data, system maintenance, and long-term operation are unclear. The Living Lab model proves effective as a governance accelerator, but must be institutionalised beyond the project lifetime. Strong leadership by infrastructure authorities and corridor managers is a decisive enabler of exploitation.

Risk analysis confirms that the main threats to exploitation are not technological, but institutional: fragmented responsibilities, unclear funding mechanisms, resistance to data sharing, and lack of long-term mandates. Mitigation requires early alignment with policy frameworks, integration into public procurement processes, and explicit linkage to EU priorities on resilience, climate adaptation, and digital infrastructure.

Finally, CRISTAL's exploitation roadmap shows strong alignment with European regulation, future calls and policy directions. By positioning its results within ALICE recommendations and DINA principles, CRISTAL does not only propose exploitable technologies, but also **a transferable exploitation blueprint** for inland waterways across Europe.

In conclusion, CRISTAL's exploitation potential is real and credible, provided that results are scaled through **public-private cooperation, corridor-level governance, and phased implementation**. The project demonstrates that exploitation in IWT is not about selling products, but about **building durable digital and institutional infrastructures** that enable long-term resilience, competitiveness, and sustainability.

6.3.2. Recommendations

Adopt Phased, Corridor-Level Deployment Strategies

CRISTAL demonstrates that exploitation is most effective when technologies are deployed incrementally at corridor level. Therefore:

- Deployment should start with high-value, low-complexity functions (alerts, monitoring, forecasting).
- More advanced functionalities (e.g., full synchromodal re-routing) should be introduced only after trust and data maturity are established.
- Pilot results should be scaled along entire corridors, rather than replicated as isolated sites.

Phased deployment reduces risk, increases stakeholder acceptance, and builds sustainable demand.

Institutionalise Living Labs as Permanent Governance Instruments

The Living Lab approach proved essential for aligning technology, governance, and business logic. It should therefore be:

- Institutionalised within infrastructure authorities and corridor management structures.
- Used beyond R&I projects as a continuous co-creation and validation mechanism.
- Linked to decision-making processes, investment planning, and system evolution.

This ensures that innovation remains embedded in real operational contexts and does not stall after project completion.

Clarify Data Governance, Ownership, and Responsibilities Early

A recurring risk identified in CRISTAL is uncertainty around data ownership and long-term system operation. To mitigate this:

- Data governance models should be defined early, with clear roles for data providers, platform operators, and users.
- Responsibilities for system maintenance, updates, and financing beyond project lifetimes must be contractually defined.
- Open data principles should be promoted where possible, while respecting security and commercial sensitivities.

Clear governance is a prerequisite for exploitation at scale.

6.4. Strategic and Long-Term Recommendations

Embed IWT Digitalisation in Climate Adaptation Strategies

Given increasing hydrological variability, digital monitoring and forecasting tools should be:

- Explicitly integrated into national and EU **climate adaptation and resilience strategies**.
- Recognised as key instruments for managing climate risk in transport infrastructure.
- Co-financed under climate, resilience, and adaptation funding lines, not only transport budgets.

This strengthens the long-term justification for investment.

Use CRISTAL as a Reference Model for Future EU Actions

Finally, CRISTAL should be leveraged as a **reference blueprint** for future initiatives by:

- Using its governance model, exploitation logic, and business model differentiation as guidance for new calls.
- Building follow-up actions that focus on scaling, integration, and institutionalisation rather than new pilots.
- Ensuring continuity between research, deployment, and operational phases.

This will maximise the return on public investment and accelerate the transformation of European inland waterways.

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8. Appendices

Annex 1 – IPEB log spreadsheet

Partner	Background IP	Foreground IP: protectable	Foreground knowledge	Planned Current/ Future Papers?	How these results will be exploited?
Lukasiewicz-PIT	EPCIS is an open standard developed by the GS1 organisation. The implementation of the standard as software (event-based database) was conducted by the Łukasiewicz-PIT with the cooperation of the GS1 organisation. The distribution of rights to the implementation has been set at 50/50. The database constitutes know-how and together with GS1 we undertake to keep the subject matter of the contract confidential. The software code itself is a copyrighted work. L-PIT can use and is using EPCIS in a test, pilot mode and this is what we are using in CRISTAL.		The standard information exchange model for EPCIS is used. The project will develop an extension to Object Event module representing the recording of events occurring with one or more physical or digital objects. The registration of objects should fit in a standard EPCIS data exchange format which will not be copyrighted.	https://ref.gs1.org/standards/epcis/1.2.0/ (current or further?)	EPCIS will be developed as a back-up communication channel for the CRISTAL project for the transmission of messages from river buoys. If the river buoys are commercialised, it will be possible to use the system to further collect and transmit customer data on the EPCIS platform.
Lukasiewicz-PIT	Smart Buoys - know - how on integration of different internal communication protocols between buoy components using a single board computer	Protocols at the level of analysis of analogue signals sent by integrated devices.	The product in functional terms can be protected in the event of commoditisation. The work product of the L-PIT (technology integrating various communication protocols) in this case will be a company secret.	none	The product is envisaged for commercialisation for users operating on rivers where RIS is not operational, on side smaller rivers and canals. The communication and functional module of the solution will allow users to increase the navigability of the routes.
ALICE	None		Co-created policy, governance and business model insights for climate-resilient and synchromodal inland waterway logistics Stakeholder-driven roadmaps and	Integrate all public and dissemination documents within the ALICE Knowledge Platform	Integrating CRISTAL foreground knowledge into ALICE strategic research and innovation agendas (SRIA) and thematic roadmaps Using project outcomes to support policy

			<p>recommendations supporting the integration of IWT into multimodal and supply chain operations</p> <p>Contributions to exploitation, dissemination and uptake strategies, ensuring alignment with EU logistics priorities</p> <p>Consolidated lessons learned and best practices from pilots and multi-stakeholder workshops, feeding EU policy and standardisation discussions</p>	<p>Connect with other related projects during TRA in Budapest and IPIC to assess how the CRISTAL project results could leverage the other projects outcomes</p>	<p>recommendations towards the European Commission and EU Member States on resilient, low-emission logistics and Inland Waterway Transport</p> <p>Allowing wide dissemination and uptake through ALICE's European network of industry, logistics operators, ports, and technology providers</p> <p>Supporting replication and scaling of CRISTAL governance models, synchromodal concepts and best practices across European logistics corridors</p> <p>Feeding results into future Horizon Europe and innovation initiatives and cross-ETP collaboration activities</p>
ENEA	<p>Procedure for the Implementation of a Fiber Optic Sensor Chain and Fiber Optic Sensor Chain: Patent: 102022000007103 (Italy)</p> <p>https://www.mdpi.com/books/reprint/2532-fiber-optic-sensors-for-structural-and-geotechnical-monitoring</p>	Work in progress	<p>The exploitation strategy aims to patent, commercialize, and deploy the CRISTAL fiber-optic sensor system to enable uninterrupted, real-time detection of sediment accumulation buildup in free-flowing waterways, thereby supporting informed decision-making on the navigability of high-risk sections.</p>	<p>n D. Vicca et al 2025 JINST 20 C05018</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/20/05/C05018</p>	<p>The results will be exploited by advancing the patented CRISTAL fiber-optic sensor technology toward commercialization, large-scale deployment, and integration into waterway management systems. This will enable continuous, real-time monitoring of sediment and obstruction buildup in free-flowing waterways, provide actionable intelligence on the navigability of critical sections, and support authorities and infrastructure managers in predictive maintenance, risk mitigation, and safer navigation operations</p>
AIPo	All information data about the state of River Po navigability condition is public	None	<p>The statistical model for navigability prediction can be shared on request with other public navigation managers. Knowledge of the Italian IWW scenario. Relationship with several Italian IWW stakeholders.</p>	None, at the moment	<p>Stakeholder will be able to download the Smart Bulletin from both the AIPo website and the "Il Portolano del Po" App</p>
Fraunhofer	<p>DT Waterlevel: builds on data sources and the APIs for accessing pre-existing historic hydrological and real-time river discharge data,</p>	<p>DT Waterlevel: source code of these DT is not shared</p> <p>DT Locks / DT Buoy: This</p>	<p>Waterlevel DT: waterlevel prediction models can be shared on request; predicted results for the waterlevels</p> <p>DT Locks / DT Buoy: This includes more</p>	<p>Planned papers in 2025:</p> <p>ETC 2025: Abstract handed in</p>	<p>SCMS and pilots; results from the CRISTAL project will be used for further research and to extend the functionalities for other use cases. Additionally, the DTs could be</p>

	<p>forming the foundation for advanced prediction tools</p> <p>DT Locks / DT Buoy: At this point, knowledge of software architecture, software development and similar topics are relevant at most. The rest was developed and acquired in the course of the project.</p>	<p>is somewhat more difficult to answer from the DT perspective, as the sensor data is handled and processed here, so if certain restrictions apply there, e.g. for the AE system, they should also apply here. So it depends on the technology providers. In relation to DT, this is developed software that does not have to/cannot be patented in the first approach.</p>	<p>or less the entire development of the DT, which was created from scratch based on the requirements and scenarios with the various technologies.</p>	<p>IPIC 2025: Abstract in preparation IAME 2025: Paper in preparation in collaboration with Ernest Czemanski</p>	<p>used for other waterways.</p>
UNEW	<p>Knowhow on GPR use for infrastructure assets (achieved through previous projects and PhD stages - 2 students). Algorithms and tools for data processing and visualisation.</p>	<p>Potential patent royalties if EUMO would consider applying for a patent to protect the subsurface inspection system (SIR) as a whole (inc. design of modular platform, data collection and processing method, etc.), or just elements of SIR system and inspection methodology.</p>	<p>In-depth knowledge on operating GPR equipment and subsequent processing of acquired data. Including use of specialised software, data processing methods, visualisation tools and algorithms. Knowledge on design and operation of complex systems for inspection of large infrastructure assets. Knowledge on maintenance practice for large IWW infrastructure assets. Including types of damages and their causes, maintenance operations, inspection methods, etc. Knowledge on management of complex big data (inc. media files resulting from processing of GPR scanning data). Including use of Digital Twin solution for the scope (interfaces, data transfer, communication protocols, etc.). In-depth knowledge on assessment and technical validation of sensor-based systems at different TRLs, vs KPIs and</p>	<p>1 paper published https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2025.3530758 1 PhD thesis completed (using outcomes from CRISTAL) 1 paper at TRA 2024 conference, awarded a prize in TRA Visions Contest (2nd prize for Waterborne) 1 planned paper based on final results/ activities in 2025</p>	<p>Further publications to increase visibility and credibility of researchers involved in CRISTAL. Use of achieved knowledge in postgraduate teaching, and formal integration in future curriculae. Use of knowledge and skills for further similar work in potential research projects in transport area or civil engineering.</p>

			requirements, testing methods, test planning, etc.		
SOGESCA	None		Living Lab methodology. Stakeholders engagement process. Stakeholders' assessment on management systems, business continuity, climate-change problems related, mitigation and adaptation actions, ESG reports, involvement of public authorities.	1 published paper in PORTUSplus the Journal of RETE, N. 17 – 2024 , Year XIV, Issue “Research Themes”, RETE Publisher, Venice ISSN: 2039-6422	This document was presented to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport and shared with the entire community of stakeholders in the Padano-Veneto waterway system. Together with the Manifesto for Sustainable Development, it can serve as a guideline for ensuring future improvement of the entire system.
UnAnt	None	None	Existing knowledge regarding IWT and transport economics in general. Knowledge obtained via other R&D projects and other funded research projects.	paper accepted	integration into postgraduate teaching, add to scientific knowledge through papers
UnGda	Business models for implementing IWW into supply chains into environment excluding inland navigation due to unsatisfied capacity/performance.	Verified business models implementing IWW into supply chains with special focus on project cargo and dry bulk cargo in direct services to/from seaport	Business model insights for climate-resilient and synchromodal inland waterway logistics recommendation and policy. New socio-economic knowledge on IWT perception in Poland.	2 papers published and presented on scientific conferences. 1 book published. 1 book in preparation. 1 paper submitted for IAME 2025 and presented on the conference in Bergen/Norway Jun. 2025. 1 paper in preparation for TRA 2026	Additional knowledge for further development and academic purposes - teaching.
VNF	All information about the state of VNF infra (bad or good condition, % of risk of failure) is confidential.	All information about the state of VNF infra (bad or good condition, % of risk of failure) is confidential.	Stakeholder-driven roadmaps and recommendations supporting the integration of IWT into multimodal and supply chain operations	None	French buoys could be further investigated in other projects; Fluv'IOTe could be further investigated with national authorities ; SIR technology could be further investigated and tested internally as a maintenance tool ; the living lab approach could be further implemented into other projects

KTI	None	None	Know-how and lessons learnt on strengthening inland waterway transport resilience (governance, stakeholder coordination, and uptake pathways). Contributions to the project exploitation, dissemination and communication strategy, ensuring alignment with EU inland navigation and multimodal logistics priorities and with national policy needs.	Yes. KTI plans peer-reviewed journal and conference publications building on CRISTAL results (resilience, governance and decision-support for IWT), complemented by policy briefs/technical notes (open access where applicable and in line with the Grant Agreement).	We continue the dissemination of results and encouraging IWT usage and uptake beyond project closure by: (i) mainstreaming CRISTAL results into Hungarian transport strategy development and policy advisory processes; (ii) embedding the knowledge in the academic knowledge base through publications, teaching materials and further research; (iii) sustaining the triple-helix cooperation by transferring practical insights to industry and public authorities via follow-up workshops, targeted stakeholder exchanges and guidance material; and (iv) leveraging the outcomes in follow-up EU and national R&I proposals/projects.
CERTH	None	None	Consolidated lessons learned and best practices from pilots and multi-stakeholder workshops, feeding EU policy and standardisation discussions	1) Acoustic Conference "Detection of Acoustic Emission Events in Metal Water Lock Gates in River" T. Tsenis, V.Kappatos. 2) Infrastructures under review "Clustering and Vectorizing Acoustic Emissions of Large Infrastructures' Normal Operation" T Tsenis and V. Kappatos	Corresponding service provided in predictive maintenance of large to very large infrastructures. Further use and development in other EU projects for large infrastructures.
CERTH	None	CERTH retains all Intellectual Property rights to the SCMS and its functionalities. In addition, no patent has been filed at the	Algorithms for route planning, data standardisation algorithm	A paper is submitted for TRA2026 (Synchronodal Network Transport Management System adaptability	Use of the SCMS in the project pilot sites beyond the project duration and further development of the system from CERTH through future EU projects.

		moment, however, the synchromodal route planning algorithm that was developed is not shared		for inland navigation. Lessons from Po river, Italy)	
UniCa	None	None	Knowledge of the Italian IWW scenario. Relationship with several Italian IWW stakeholders.	None, at the moment	To support and promote an increased use of inland waterways for both goods and passengers, as a reliable, efficient and eco-sustainable transport mode in alternative but also in synergies with road and rail transport.
UniTra	see above	see above	see above	see above	see above
EUMO	TUNNEL VISION knowhow. Knowledge of the operation of ground penetrating radar for rail infrastructure, particularly tunnels.	The radar system developed in CRISTAL-Subsurface inspection Radar (SIR) is not patentable as a complete system as it builds on existing innovative technologies. The system under development is a trade secret and will not be disclosed to avoid early competition. However, SIR can certainly be exploited for market opportunities: together with the algorithms developed and owned by UNEW.	Excellent knowledge of the practical application of radar in complex infrastructure and real-life working environment. Excellent skills in the design, development and fabrication of subsurface radar testing equipment. SIR system currently not patentable as it builds on existing innovative technologies, but can be exploited for market opportunities; algorithms developed by UNEW may be owned by UNEW, however there may be security/ confidentiality issued with regard to VNF data (not just with regard to locks) : further exploitation of SSRI on any surface may be viable commercially using first adopter advantage : UNEW and EUMO have joint ownership of WP2 SSRI results	paper published, others will be published subject to sensitivity and confidentiality	There is an emerging commercial arrangement with VNF which recognises the security/ confidentiality issues with regard to VNF data (not just with regard to locks). This arrangement is based on VNF collecting the SIR data using the SIR equipment left by EUMO with VNF for their validation of the data collection system on different locks. The radar-based non-destructive sub-surface inspection system (SIR) was designed, developed and validated for examination and inspection of IWW infrastructure assets, e.g., the sheer vertical concrete walls integral to lock infrastructure. The use of this advanced technology to assess the integrity of the inspected assets and provide information on their condition will enable preventive and/or predictive maintenance. KER5 The next step is for EUMO to move forward from the preproduction prototype demonstrated on the Seine and Moselle and us the lessons learnt to produce a robust commercial system that

D11.3 Final business and economic assessment and exploitation plans

					<p>can be easily transported for use on lock structures and other IWW infrastructures such as dams.</p> <p>Further exploitation of SIR on any surface may be viable commercially using first adopter advantage.</p>
IV	None	<p>Feasibility study report for cold ironing facilities along relevant IWWs managed by IV (copyright); detailed design documents for typical plants at 4 landing points (trade secret)</p>	None	None, at the moment	<p>The knowledge acquired through the studies realized within the framework of CRISTAL project will be more than useful in order to define some future steps of development of such kind of infrastructures along the IWW managed by IV.</p>

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